

COVERING THE EMBASSY ISSUES OF THE KOKAND KHANATE IN HISTORICAL SOURCE "ANJUM AT-TAVORIX"

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Annotation: *The article deals with the issue of coverage of embassy relations in the work "Anjam at-tavorix" by Khudoyorkhanzoda, one of the important sources in the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate.*

Keywords: *Kokand, ambassador, friendship, conspiracy, purpose.*

INTRODUCTION.

Although the history of the embassy of the Kokand khanate has not been studied in a comprehensive way, some scholars who have studied the history of the Kokand khanate A.Urinbaev, R.N.Nabiev, A.Juvonmardiev, H.Ziyoev, H.Bobobekov, T.Q.Beysembiev, Sh.Vohidov, V.Ishquvvatov, Z.Ilkhomov, O.Sultonov, Sh.Mahmudov, B. Tursunov, Sh.Kuldashev, T.Khudoykulov, B.Babadjanov, M.Akhmedova and others also touched on khanate embassy relations [1.1.]. For the first time, the history of embassy relations in the Kokand Khanate is analyzed in manuscript sources. There are about 40 manuscripts created by local historians in the study of the history of the Kokand khanate.

The only author's copy of "Anjam at-tavorix" is R. N. It was presented to Nabiev in about 1940 by T. Mirgiyosov. In 1958, R. At Nabiev's request, Anjum at-Tavorix was copied from this manuscript by a senior researcher at the Abu Rayhan Beruni Institute of Oriental Studies, Candidate of Historical Sciences, calligrapher Abdulkadir Murodov. The name of the author of "Anjam at-tavorix" remains unclear because it is not mentioned anywhere in the work. According to Kokand historians R.Nabiev, H.Bobobekov, Sh.Vakhidov, this work may belong to the pen of Muhammadamin or Ibn Yamin, one of the five sons of Khudoyorkhan. Therefore, the calligrapher A. Murodov, who copied this work, noted that the author of the work was Khudoyorkhanzoda [p. 3.1.3]. The work was translated from Persian-Tajik into Uzbek by a well-known orientalist,

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS: MAIN PART (MAIN PART). Khudoyorkhanzoda's work "Anjam at-tavorix" contains information about about thirty diplomatic relations, including the diplomatic relations of

the Kokand khans with Bukhara, Khiva, the Turkish Sultanate, China and Kashgar. The play also includes embassy relations that are not related to the history of the Kokand Khanate. For example, the diplomatic relations between the reign of Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur and the diplomatic relations between Bukhara and the Emir of Afghanistan were mentioned. [3.2.99-b; 266-b.].

It is expedient to analyze the embassy relations of the Kokand khanate mentioned in this play in five types:

- high-level, friendly embassy relations;
- embassy relations, which began with hostility and ended with a wedding;

- preparation, embassy relations, which ended in a conspiracy; this type of embassy relationship is also evident in the history of all states, and often results in a genocidal war. There were many examples of this in the political life of the Kokand khanate.

- embassy relations, beginning with enmity and ending with friendship or reconciliation (or armies of the Kokand khan);

- Embassy relations begin with friendship and end with war.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. While studying the work "Anjum at-tavorix", we come across the embassy relations, the result of which ended in friendship, the desired goal was achieved. This can be exemplified by the first group of embassy relations. In fact, the embassy was sent to Kokand by the Emir of Bukhara to turn the Sino-Kipchak uprising into a truce. Khudoyorkhonzoda did not specify the date of sending the ambassadors. The attitude of the embassy is as follows: Ismatillo Dadkhoh from Bukhara comes as an ambassador with valuable gifts. On the 3rd day, the ambassador was allowed to kiss on the doorstep, perform the embassy etiquette with maturity, pass the gifts through the eyes of the chemist, and be blessed with benevolent kindness and compliments. He stayed as a guest for a few more days and was allowed to leave. They gave worthy gifts and presents to the Emir of Bukhara and sent them to the ambassador with Azimboy Dadkhoh [3.3. 254-b.]. When they reached Nurato's tomb, the Emir of the tomb, aware of their arrival, sent them to meet the governor of Nurato. He invited them to the fortress of Yangikurgan and showed them a lot of respect. Then they exhorted the pand to calm the Chinese, Kipchak, Karakalpak categories. After Azimboy said that all of them had been saved, they all returned to their homes. Azimboy took his grandfather to Bukhara and allowed him to return, rejoicing in the royal blessings and compliments. Ismatullo Dadkhoh came to Kokand again with valuable gifts and a horse.

After living in the capital for a while, the ambassador was sent to Bukhara with Sultanhojayi Ato (pseudonym) with large gifts. Embassy relations between Bukhara and Fergana have been established several times, and as a result of this solidarity, the Karakalpak and Chinese-Kipchak factions have calmed down, and the enemies and destroyers of both properties have been repulsed. The friends of the two estates, on the other hand, were at peace at the address of Kamron [p. 3.4.25].

It is known from the work of Khudoyorkhonzoda that in the history of the Kokand khanate there were embassy relations, which began with hostility and ended with a wedding. After the capture of Samarkand by Abdurahimbi, scholars and high-ranking people from the Bukhara khan visited him as ambassadors, and the emirs of the two sides began peace talks. According to him, Samarkand and Kattakurgan will pass to Abdurahim Fergani. They will not be sued by the Bukhara khan. The ruler of Fergana was satisfied with this, acknowledging that he would not take a single step forward from Kattakurgan, and embellished the sealed treaty. The ambassadors of Bukhara returned home happy with donations and gifts. The Kokand khan began to occupy Shakhrisabz. The governor of Shakhrisabz, Hakimbek Mangit, sent his ambassadors to Kokand with many greetings and congratulations after hearing that the people of Bukhara and Kokand had made peace. In his congratulatory message, he said that he was obedient to the Kokand khan and had a hand in it. The ambassadors perform the rituals with weakness and obedience. The khan's compassion inspires them and gives them many gifts. Through them, Hakimbek presents Mangyt with a sword decorated with jewels. Abdujabbor, together with the ambassadors, sends a gift to the daughter of Hakimbek's brother Ibrahimbek. Hakimbek conducts the banquet and hospitality with great respect. Oychuchukoyim bint Ibrokhimbek sent Valina to Samarkand to Abdurahimkhan with valuable fabrics, jewels and many gifts. Hostility and hostility end in such kinship because of embassy relations [3.5.98.]. The ambassadors who brought this great girl were honored and returned to Hakimbek with innumerable gifts. Although not related to embassy relations, let us cite the following incidents. In 1146/1733, when Abdurahimbi set out to conquer Tashkent and Turkestan, he died of a disease in Khojand at the age of 36. He has two wives, 1 Erdonabek from Sharafniso, Mrs. Khurshid, Mrs. Zebuniso, and 2 Mrs. Oyjon from Oychuchukoyim. He died of the disease at the age of 36 in Khojand. He has two wives, 1 Erdonabek from Sharafniso, Mrs. Khurshid, Mrs. Zebuniso, and 2 Mrs. Oyjon from Oychuchukoyim. He died of the disease at the age of

36 in Khojand. He has two wives, 1 Erdonabek from Sharafniso, Mrs. Khurshid, Mrs. Zebuniso, and 2 Mrs. Oyjon from Oychuchukoyim.

In the work "Anjum at-tavorix" there are a lot of conspiracies, conspiracies and unintentional embassy relations. While the Kokand khan was fighting with the governor of Tashkent Yunuskhodja, the governor of Uratepa Bobek was killed by his nephew Bekmurod and took over the governorship. Fearing the wrath of the Kokand khan for this, he sent a letter to the Emir of Bukhara, Haidar. The main content of his letter was to state that he was subordinate to him. Of course, Amir Haidar would be very happy about this, because he would benefit from it politically and economically. After Bekmurod sent his trusted envoy to the envoy, he himself followed them [p. 3.6.170]. When Bekmurod was pleased to receive Amir Haydar's greetings, he handed him over to Bobek's son to take his father's blood. The purpose of the embassy in this example was to try to save his life by deceit, to hide his betrayal of his relatives, and as a result he did not achieve his goal.

Khudoyorkhanzoda's work has another interesting embassy approach to the conspiracy, the mention of which serves to study the history of the Kokand Khanate in depth. When Olimkhan besieged the Jizzakh fortress, Sultankhoja came from Tashkent and surrounded Shahidon. When Olimkhan Sultanhoja's destruction came to him as more important, he retreated. Then Alimkhan sent his brother Umarchan after him. When Umarchan arrived in Toytepa, an envoy on behalf of Sultankhodja came to him and told him that tomorrow he would come to kiss the hand of Sultankhodja khan, who was seen on the bank of the Chirchik river, the crescent of the victorious army. This ambassador is received with honor (because he brought the gospel), and at the time of his departure he is sent with his envoys. The khan also begins to come along the Chirchik River.

It is obvious that the above embassy attitude is a conspiracy. We would like to remind you that the subsequent events have been dangerous, noting that the result of the embassy relationship, which is a combination of fraud, deceit, and malicious intent, may end in destruction. After the siege of Tashkent by the enraged Umarchan, the city scholars, who were left without water, bowed to him and apologized, and released the ambassador [p. 3.8.178]. Umarchan also captured Niyazbek fortress.

Khudoyorkhanzoda Anjum at-tavorix reported that after the defeat of the governor of Tashkent Yunuskhodja Kokand khan, he sent his ambassador with valuable gifts to the Emir of Bukhara to reconcile with him [3.9.173-p.]. In doing so, the ambassadors may have done well in an embassy relationship

that ended well, or ended because they had achieved their goals. The governor of Tashkent asked the Emir of Bukhara to send at the same time masters of making cannons and rifles. The Emir of Bukhara greets the ambassadors with respect. He also sent some of the Afghan and Iranian masters of artillery and weapons to the governor of Tashkent. Thus, the two sides, which considered the Kokand khanate as a common enemy, the Tashkent khokimiyat and the Bukhara emirate, tried to unite for a common goal.

The following situation is mentioned in the work "Anjum at-tavorix" in the history of the Kokand khanate, which began with enmity and ended with friendship or reconciliation. When Khudoyorbek, the governor of Uratapa, died, his brother Bobobek was appointed governor of Fergana. Then the khan of Bukhara Shokhmurod began to march to Uratapa. Upon hearing this, the Kokand khan immediately arrived with a large army. Bukhara khan Musahoja Dahbediy, who settled in a place called Koshtegirmon, was sent as an ambassador to Kokand khan. The ambassador arrived in Khojand and was admitted to the khan's presence three days later. "Eloquence, with its eloquent and sweet words, good manners and rituals, freezes the embassy, brings evidence and documents from the verses and hadiths for peace, and softens the khan and his courtiers with pleasant words" [p. 3.10.153]. After the banquet, the sayyid (ambassador) is allowed to return with the owner's clothes and royal donations. In addition, the Kokand khan sent Sayyid Khokimkhoja and three trustees as his ambassadors to the Bukhara khan. These ambassadors took part in peace talks between the two countries. As a result of the truce, the fortress of Zaamin, which had already been occupied by Bukhara, was returned to Uratapa. Apparently, the hand of the Kokand khan was raised in this truce.

In the history of the Kokand khanate, embassy relations reached the peak of cultural development during the reign of Umarkhan. In 1225/1810, on the occasion of the enthronement of Umarkhan, the khans of the neighboring regions sent ambassadors of congratulations and friendship [p. 3.11.206]. Khudoyorkhanzoda's work mentions ambassadors from the Kokand khanate to Istanbul. At that time (after Umarkhan Khojand went to Uratapa and met with the locals and dignitaries) by the order of the khan, the honorable mu'in uddin al-islam, the caliph's messenger anom, the eloquent numismatic monk in the name of the great sultan Mahmudkhan jannatmakon After writing a letter, the ambassador was sent to Istanbul, the center of the caliphate, through Mir Qurban [p. 3.12.212]. At present, Sh. Mahmudov is studying the diplomatic relations of the Kokand khanate with

this state [4.1. 132-136-p.]. It is noteworthy that the scientist publishes factual information in his scientific articles on the basis of documents on diplomatic relations of the Kokand Khanate, which are kept in the "Ottoman Archive" in Turkey.

In this work of Khudoyorkhonzoda, we also see cases in the history of the Kokand khanate when embassy relations were ineffective, and the embassy attitude, which offered friendship, intensified hostility. For example, the following incident took place in Turkestan (by the armies of the Kokand Khan). . Rajab's army called on the people of this holy city to obey. But it did not help. The embassy's attitude was in vain. As Kushunbegi approached the fortress, support forces arrived from Bukhara. Encouraged, Tukay killed the ambassador and his companions. Then the neighbor becomes angry and intensifies the military march. This can be an example of an embassy relationship that invites friendship to intensify hostility. As a result, Tukay fled to Samarkand, and his family members were executed. After Turkestan subjugated Dashti Kipchak to the khanate, his neighbor returned to Tashkent.

Information about the implementation of embassy relations in the Kokand khanate is also mentioned in the work "Anjum at-tavorih". For example, one of them is that Odiltora sent his son to Kokand khan as an ambassador. Odiltora, a descendant of Abulhairkhan, lived with his nomadic tribes in China and Russia. He sent his son to the Khan of Kokand and asked him to ensure that he lived in this Islamic territory, so that this year the Emir would pay all the divan marsumat (taxes) to the Islamic treasury year after year, without quarreling and without delay. This request is accepted and the ambassador-child is rewarded with royal blessings and happily returns [pp. 3.14.217-218]. This incident also led to the formation of friendly relations between the two sides.

According to the details of the events mentioned in Khudoyorkhonzoda, we are convinced that the political and economic ties between the Kokand Khanate and the Khiva Khanate were strong. This is because the embassy relations between the two countries do not have any negative consequences. Khudoyorkhonzoda: "Muhammad Rahimkhan, an ambassador from Khorezmi, came to the palace of honor to congratulate Turkestan and Dashti Kipchak on their conquest, inviting them to alliance and unification with royal gifts and presents, as well as a letter full of love. After staying in Huzand for a few days, Izzat received permission to leave after hospitality and hospitality, and sent Abdul Khaliq's guard (chief of guards) with him to Khorezm with gifts and letters "[p. 3.1.218]. .

Anjum at-Tavorix also contains examples of the establishment of diplomatic relations between the Kokand khanate and another state: Haji Mir Qurban, who was ambassador to Istanbul, presented the sultan's favor to Sultan Mahmud of Fergana, the Turkish sultan. He achieved his goal and on the way will be in Khorezm in the presence of Khiva khan. He arrived in Kokand with an envoy of the khan. The ambassador of the Khiva khan was well received, stayed for a few days, and then returned to Khiva with the khan's permission [p. 3.16.229].

In the play, the ruler of Shakhrisabz, Daniel Parvanachi, on behalf of the saint Yasovulboshi, sent an envoy to Kokand khan, Umarchan Chin (China) as an ambassador of Zuhur devonbegi, although not related to the history of Kokand khanate. It was also reported that he and his commanders were visiting the Emir of Bukhara Nasrullo and that the incident took a negative turn.

According to Khudoyorkhonzoda, one of Umarchan's sons, Sultan Mahmudbek, was kidnapped in Shakhrisabz for taking part in the uprising and married the governor's daughter there [3.16. 275-b.]. In 1254 / 1838-1839, Sultan Mahmud received letters from some officials in Kokand. He was encouraged to fight his brother. His father-in-law Danielbi was very happy to read this letter and sent ambassadors with gifts and a letter to Amir Nasrullo. As a result of several letters written in embassy relations, the following year Amir Nasrullo decided to attack Kokand and transfer Sultan Mahmudkhan to the khan's throne. Before the sermon, when the name of Amir Nasrudlo was read, the military was required to pay for several years, and to take part in the war against the enemies of Bukhara, Sultan Mahmud swore in front of witnesses that he agreed to these conditions. But the course of historical events did not go according to their plan. Because for some reason Umarchan's sons reconcile. Khudoyorkhonzoda recorded this event as follows: “Muhammadalikhan sent Muhammadaminbek, Mirzo Muhammadayub munshi, Mahmud Shigovul to Khojand as ambassadors to Amir Nasrullo. Khan demands that Tashkent and Turkestan, along with all its territories, be given to him. In this regard, ambassadors visited several times. (At that time, Nasrullokhan was preoccupied with the situation in Khorezm. Muhammadalikhan handed over control of Tashkent and Turkestan to his brother Sultan Mahmud, and the two became friends. [2.17.288 p.] Emir Nasrullo is angry,

In order to take strategic measures against his attack, Muhammadalikhan sent his sons Muhammadaminbek and Beklarbegi, along with two scholars, as ambassadors to Nasrullo, who was occupying

Khojand and resting in the Besharik area [p. 3.18.124]. But the emir takes them captive. In the above interrelated political events, it is divided into witnesses that the embassy relations were purposefully carried out and in some cases they ended ineffectively.

According to the tradition of the embassy, if an ambassador came from a country and he had to return to his country before his embassy term was completed, then the country had to send an ambassador to it. This custom continued until the ambassador's mission was over. For example, the khan of Bukhara Rakhimbi sent an ambassador to Kokand with gifts and letters, and the khan of Kokand sent his sister's son Khankhoja Yusufalikhoja as an ambassador to Bukhara. On his return to his homeland, the khan of Bukhara sent Yovqochtibiy with him as an ambassador [3.19.290 p.]. When he returned to Bukhara after completing his embassy duties in Kokand, Erdonabi tried to send a high-ranking official to join him. Then Khankhodja said that he wanted to go to Bukhara and study there. Yovqochtibiy and Khankhoja return to Bukhara together as the khan's ambassador. When they went to Bukhara, Rakhimbi created all the conditions for Khankhoja's education and assigned him a monthly salary. Khankhoja will stay in Bukhara for a long time.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the following can be referred to:

- In Khudoyorkhanzoda's work "Anjum at-tavorix" another important source in the study of the history of the Qoqan khanate was witnessed the attitude of the embassy in the work "Ansob as-salotin and tavorix al havoqin". It is written that the ambassador of Bukhara came to Kokand and was well received, but Sheralikhan drove him away without saying a word.

- The ambassadors who came to Kokand khans were greeted with respect in three cases: 1) If the ambassador came with good news; 2) the ambassador is polite, eloquent, intelligent; 3) comes with many valuable gifts;

- Ambassadors visiting the Kokand khanate could return to their homeland only with the permission of the khan.

-Another rule of embassy relations in the Kokand khanate is that the khan should take the gifts of the ambassadors and return them with good gifts, if he gives the gift he brought, it is an insult to the ambassador or the sender.

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DEVELOPMENT OF PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Annotation: *The article discusses the philosophical and social consciousness, the formation of philosophy as a science, the philosophical views of Central Asian thinkers.*

Keywords: *philosophy, consciousness, contemplation, man, state.*

The development of philosophy has a long history and is a special form of philosophical and social consciousness. Philosophy is the oldest and most interesting of human knowledge. Philosophy is the most ancient science, and its emergence dates back to the era of ancient slavery. Sources indicate that philosophy as a science was originally formed and developed in India, China, Greece, and Central Asian countries. Philosophy, its subject, the object of study, the problems of philosophy are issues that have long been of interest to scientists. Initially, philosophy encompassed not only the knowledge gained from people's life observations, but also their own thoughts about the universe. Thoughts on the subject of philosophy have changed over time, and philosophical understanding of the world has been expressed in various forms. Fans, the development of spiritual culture has had its influence on philosophy. Initially, the concept of philosophy was a symbol of "science" and was used in the broadest sense of "science". In ancient Greece, an attempt was made to define the subject of philosophy. The classification of sciences is an example of this. The subject of philosophical debate has been covered by medieval thinkers in Central Asia.

Abu Nasir al-Farabi said, "Philosophy is the essence of being; perfect and complete about the content of all that exists; the science that imparts knowledge. If the knowledge of existence is acquired, if it is taught about it, if the essence of the thing is known, if the meaning of the thing is understood, if there is a kind of belief and imagination in the brain on the basis of reliable evidence and documents, we call this knowledge philosophy ... , has created many works on philosophical problems. These are "The Word of Substance" ("The Word of the Word"), "The Book of Laws" ("The Book of the Doom Navomis"), and "The Word of the Meaning of the

Concept of Philosophy." (Kamal doil means the name as-philosophy), The Book on the Necessity of Philosophy, The Origin and Classification of Sciences (Ija-al-umum).

Continuing the thought of Abu Ali Ibn Sina al-Farabi, the task of philosophy is to examine all existing things, the order of their origin, their interrelationships, the transition from one to another. Abu Ali Ibn Sina's philosophical views such as the Kitab al-Shifa, the Encyclopaedia, the Law of Medical Sciences, as well as the Risala al-Tayir (The Science of Kunt), Salomat wa Ipsal, and Hayit Ibn Yaqsan. found expression in his art pockets. Abu Abdullah al-Khwarizmi believes that philosophy consists of two parts, theoretical and practical. According to him, theoretical philosophy includes the natural sciences, theology, ie metaphysics and logic. In general, in the Middle Ages, the view that philosophy was a science of science was prevalent. One of the objects of study of philosophy and the most important is man. Man, his nature, attitude to the world, language, ethics, forms of manifestation of human abilities have fascinated philosophers. Socrates (ancient Greek philosopher) emphasized that philosophy is the understanding of life. A number of treatises by Aristotle, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Farabi, Beruni, and Descartes are devoted to the philosophical understanding of man. These include Abu Ali ibn Sina's On the Sciences and Hegel's Philosophy of the World. In general, the scope of philosophical problems includes the world, its structure, nature, society, man, man's place in society, man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Does it have boundaries?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them. Socrates (ancient Greek philosopher) emphasized that philosophy is the understanding of life. A number of treatises by Aristotle, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Farabi, Beruni, and Descartes are devoted to the philosophical understanding of man. These include Abu Ali ibn Sina's On the Sciences and Hegel's Philosophy of the World. In general, the scope of philosophical problems includes the world, its structure, nature, society, man, man's place in society, man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Does it have boundaries?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them. Socrates (ancient Greek philosopher) emphasized that philosophy is the understanding of life. A number of treatises by Aristotle, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Farabi, Beruni, and Descartes are devoted to the philosophical

understanding of man. These include Abu Ali ibn Sina's On the Sciences and Hegel's Philosophy of the World. In general, the scope of philosophical problems includes the world, its structure, nature, society, man, man's place in society, man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Is there a limit to it?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them. A number of Descartes' treatises are devoted to the philosophical understanding of man. These include Abu Ali ibn Sina's On the Sciences and Hegel's Philosophy of the World. In general, the scope of philosophical problems includes the world, its structure, nature, society, man, man's place in society, man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Does it have boundaries?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them. A number of Descartes' treatises are devoted to the philosophical understanding of man. These include Abu Ali ibn Sina's On the Sciences and Hegel's Philosophy of the World. In general, the scope of philosophical problems includes the world, its structure, nature, society, man, man's place in society, man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Does it have boundaries?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them. such as man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Does it have boundaries?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them. such as man's understanding of the universe. That is why from ancient times people have asked, "What is the world?", "How is it structured?", "Does it have boundaries?", "Why do the world change in different ways?", "What is society?" ? » who asked questions such as and sought answers to them.

In conclusion, it can be said that the formation and development of philosophy, the philosophical worldview, is connected with the development of society, social life. The historical roots of the revival of philosophy as a science go back to ancient times. Philosophy is of great importance in the correct understanding of the world and reality. The human worldview is first of all reflected in his spiritual world, in the culture of thinking, of the correct understanding of vocabulary.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV'S SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE KOKAN KHANATE

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Annotation: *The article details the importance of the scientific heritage of the famous scientist Asomiddin Urinbaev in the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate.*

Keywords: *Orientalist, Kokand, source, manuscript, catalog*

Sources are important in the study of the political, economic and cultural life of the Kokand Khanate, which developed as a state in 1709-1876. Because the authors of the sources described the events that lived in the territory of the khanate and saw with their own eyes. While the study of the history of the Kokand khanate is recognized as one of the most pressing problems in the history of Uzbek statehood, the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Urinbaev is of great importance in this regard. When world scholars recognized Asomiddin Urinbaev as a Temurid and Orientalist, it is known that he was a researcher who made a great contribution to the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate. For the first time, the scientist conducted research on the work of Muhammad Salihhoja Tashkendi "History of Tashkent" [2.1.]. In subsequent research by Asomiddin Urinbaev Abu Ubaydullo Tashkendi's "Summary of the situation" [3.1.], "History" by Muhyiddin Khokandi [4.1.], Imomali qori Kunduz (Kohanduzi) 's "Tavorihi manzuma" [5.1.], Muhammad Fozilbek's "Perfect history of Fergana" [6.1.], Mulla Niyaz Muhammad's "History of Shahrukh" [7.1.], Mirza Olim Mushrif's "Ansob as-salotin and tavorix al-havoqin" [8.1.], Avaz Muhammad Attor's "Historical Worldview" [9.1.].

According to Academician D. Yusupova, in 1964, 1971, 1987 Asomiddin Urinbaev and LM Epifanova prepared collections of Oriental manuscripts. Asomiddin Urinbaev personally participated in the creation of volumes VII, IX, XI of the collection of Oriental manuscripts and edited them. He reviewed the manuscript sources on the history of the Kokand Khanate included in these volumes one by one and created the descriptions of the sources in the catalogs.

It is expedient to divide the level of study of Asomiddin Urinbaev's researches on the history of Kokand khanate into three groups. The first

group during the Soviet era published works are included. The second group consists of research published during independence, and the third group includes articles and works of foreign researchers covering some issues of the history of the Kokand Khanate.

The authors of the first group include A. Mukhtorov [10.1.], A. Khasanov [11.1.], F. Gofforov [12.1.], V. Ploskikh [13.1.], Sh. Vakhidov [14.1.] And others.

In his research, A. Mukhtorov used Asomiddin Urinbaev's scientific articles to cover the history of Uratopa during his time in the Kokand Khanate. The researcher also relied on Asomiddin Urinbaev, who translated the original manuscripts covering the history of the political, economic, social and cultural life of the Middle Ages.

In covering the history of Kyrgyzstan, A. Khasanov elaborated on the article by Asomiddin Urinbaev in the analysis of changes in the political and economic life of the territories of the Kokand Khanate. Based on the translation of the information given in the work "Khulosat ul-akhvol", it is described that the daily life of the cattle-breeding population, various pressures on them by the khan's officials, led to the uprising.

F. Gofforov's research covers the economic life of the khanate, and in the analysis of domestic and foreign trade relations, economic relations between Russia and Kokand, Asomiddin Urinbaev draws on the findings of local historians.

In the section of V.K. the response of the officials is highlighted [13.2.262.].

In his research included in this group, Sh.

The second group of literature includes researches published and carried out after the independence of Uzbekistan, including Sh. Researchers such as Mahmudov [19.1.], H. Burieva [20.1.], B. Babadjanov [21.1.], Z. Khatamova [22.1.] Can be listed.

Asomiddin Urinbaev is mentioned as a scholar who studied the sources on the history of the Kokand Khanate. "A. Urinbaev recognized in his time that" Khulosat ul-akhvol "is a very important source in the study of the history of the khanate," said Sh. Vahidov. [15.2.]

As K. Vakhidova's research is directly related to the sources, the comparative analysis is based on two articles by Asomiddin Urinbaev.

Z. Ilkhomov stopped Asomiddin Urinbaev's scientific researches in the process of analyzing the period of occupation of the Kokand khanate of the Russian Empire [17.2.16 p.].

When describing the history of the study of the work "History of Tashkent" U. Sultanov referred to the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Urinbaev

[18.2.7p.]. It is noted that the life of the author, the history of the work, its geographical names were first revealed by Asomiddin Urinbaev and O. Buriev.

Sh. Mahmudov referred to the research of Asomiddin Urinbaev in the analysis of officials in the administrative management of the Kokand Khanate, their appointment, taxation and taxation in the country [19.2.110p.].

H. Burieva draws conclusions based on the research of Asomiddin Urinbaev in the coverage of the history of Tashkent and the analysis of the origin of place names in the city. Muhammad Salihkhoja emphasized the in-depth analysis of the information on the toponymy of the city of Tashkent [p. 20.2.5; p. 10]. For example, the topography of Tashkent consisting of four districts and the geography of the surrounding lands included in the scope of these administrative units are based on the work "History of Tashkent" in the interpretation of Asomiddin Urinbaev and O. Buriev [20.3.29 p.]. The table on naming the gates of Tashkent in different sources is based on the work of H. Burieva Asomiddin Urinbova and O. Buriev "Tashkent in the classification of Muhammad Salih" [20.4.34 p.].

In B.Babadjanov's research such issues as formation of Kokand khanate, political, economic, cultural development, chronological analysis of rulers were studied, and Asomiddin Urinbaev's researches on the history of Kokand khanate were widely used [21.2.722 p.].

Z.Khatamova's scientific articles note that Asomiddin Urinbaev left a scientific legacy that provides information about the economic life of the Kokand khanate, which is important in all areas of the history of the khanate. In an in-depth study of the khanate's tax system, Asomiddin Urinbaev compares the information in this area with the information in the works of Russian historians [22.2.].

The third group of the level of study of the study consists of literature published in foreign countries, which includes J. Tulibaeva and G. Isaxan¹, S.Emishbaev, Dj. It is possible to include researches of foreign scientists such as Abdukarimov, J.Alimbaev.

J.Tulibaeva and G. Volumes VII, IX, XI of the collection of Oriental manuscripts prepared by Asomiddin Urinbaev and LM Epifanova were widely used in Isakhan's research. J.Tulibaeva and G. The Isakhans considered these catalogs in terms of covering the history of Kyrgyzstan in sources related to the history of the Kokand Khanate.

¹Tulibaeva J., Isaxan G. Arabographic sources on the history of Kazakhstan: Fond instituta vostokovedenie Akademik nauk Respubliki Uzbekistan. - Astana, 2013. - 154p.

In conclusion, it should be noted that an analysis of the three groups of literature in Qori shows that the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate still refers to the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Urinbaev. Therefore, this situation serves as a key factor indicating the need for ongoing research.

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JECTION AND TECHNICAL DRAWING

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Annotation: *This article discusses the importance of studying axonometry, teaching the types of axonometric projection, the use of exhibitions in teaching the topic of axonometric projection, technical drawing and its implementation, techniques of three-dimensional expression.*

Key words: *axonometric projection, methodology, architecture, building drawing, student, teacher, education.*

From a practical point of view, it may seem that there is no need to learn axonometric projections and technical drawings based on them: in production they are rarely used, but in architecture and construction drawing they are used more often. But there are at least two arguments in favor of the need to include this topic in the school drawing course.

Firstly, it is a great educational value of axonometric projections. First of all, it is an excellent tool for developing and training spatial imagination. The implementation of axonometric projections (even manual technical drawings) clearly depicts the spatial shape and structure of the original, as if revealing the geometric skeleton of the original, and provides a useful load for the development of spatial imagination.

Axonometric projection and technical drawing are of particular interest to students who consider themselves incapable of drawing. A technical image (axonometric) reflects in one image all the information about images located in three dimensions of space. As a result, such an image is very clear, and it is almost difficult to imagine the shape of the object from the image.

Secondly, the great educational value of vivid images. Clear images serve as a link between the real object and its rectangular projections. In this case, you can prepare a series of drawing reading exercises by comparing clear images and complex drawings.

The study and implementation of clear images (axonometric projections and technical drawings) must be accompanied by the study of the system of rectangular projections and the implementation of drawings.

Because vivid imagery is the main basis for teaching students to make third projection, and with it, students can significantly perform third projection in two ways.

In the school drawing course, students learn two types of axonometric projections - curvilinear angular dimetric projections and rectangular isometric projections.

It is known that in the areas of in-depth study of engineering graphics in professional colleges, special lectures and practical classes on the topic of axonometric projections are held. In this way, the deep theoretical foundations of these imaging techniques are explored. In view of the foregoing, let us dwell on the methodology for studying the topic. Analyzing axonometric and complex diagrams in a class with students will make it easier for students to master the topic and understand the deep connections between complex and axonometric images.

To create a curved frontal dimetric projection with a model, the leading edge of the object is parallel to the projection plane, and the projected rays are directed at an acute angle to the plane. In this case, the front face is projected onto the plane in real size, and the dimensions of the side and top faces change (Fig. 67). If the edges of an object are placed in space at an angle to the plane and projected by rays perpendicular to the plane, then an isometric projection of the plane is formed (Fig.).

Similar posters can be used to explain the topic. This explains to students that axonometric projections can be made on the axis at any angle, and it will be useful to jointly analyze a poster depicting axonometric projections defined by DST.

At the same time, it is necessary to draw the attention of students to the study of which type of axonometric projection to choose, taking into account the shape of the part.

figs. Rectangular isometric shape. Methods for constructing projections of axonometric axes

On the topic of axonometric projections, it is important to teach students how to draw axes correctly and how to draw images of plane figures correctly. This is due to the fact that knowledge of the techniques for performing axonometric projections of flat geometric figures is the basis for performing axonometric projections of geometric objects, models and details. Therefore, the teacher should pay special attention to the correct formation of these skills in students. To do this, it is recommended to perform exercises on the board and in students' workbooks, use a variety of posters (forms) that reveal the content of the topic in the lesson.

Axonometric projection of plane figures
Sample Training Poster on Manufacturing Methods

The textbook describes how to perform axonometric projections of flat figures in various planes and construct isometric projections of an oval in a horizontal plane. These materials are not enough for students to master axonometric projections, especially dimetric projections.

There can be several ways to perform axonometry of objects (including technical drawings). The most common of these methods are: axonometry, starting with a flat figure forming a shape; sequential growth of parts of the subject; Sequential cutting of subject parts and combined methods. The forms contain examples of posters explaining the methods of axonometry and intended for use by the teacher in the classroom.

figs. Construct axonometry, starting with a flat figure forming a shape

Before constructing a clear image of an object, students need to systematically develop skills in analyzing its shape.

The stages of analysis of the shape of the described object can be as follows: the shape of the object is determined (prismatic and cylindrical parts); then the characteristic features of the parts are determined, i.e., the edges, protrusions, grooves and cuts that form the shape of the object. With this in mind, the exact method of imaging is determined.

figs. Production of axonometry by serial cutting

figs. Making axonometry by growing parts

Rice. Construction of a detailed axonometry by a combined method

Depending on the position of the elements of the object (from one or two or more sides), the optimal type of axonometric projection is selected: dimetry or isometry. Then the axonometric steps for each construction method are explained.

1. "From a flat figure forming a shape" (form):

- determine the shaping side and complete the drawing;
- determine the direction of the third dimension and the dimensions of the ribs;
- Determine the thickness of the described object.

2. Sequential shift method (shape):

- generalized form of the object – creation of an empty image;
- Prismatic and cylindrical (first external, then internal) scissors.

3. Method of "growing parts" (shape):

- select and describe the largest part of the object;
- growing parts of the object (first prismatic, then cylindrical).

4. Combined method (form):

- a combination of two or more methods;
- The order of movement is determined by the shape of the described

object.

When drawing axonometric images, directing students' attention to the sequence of drawing in accordance with the shape and spatial position of the object and the nature of the work being performed is quite methodologically sound, and also helps students competently perform such images.

Based on the spatial properties of the depicted object, the sequence of execution of the image and the nature of the action are determined as follows:

1. If a polyhedral object has a constant thickness, then it is advisable to perform an axonometric projection using the “flat figure formation” method;

2. Using the method of "growing parts" it is convenient to make an image of objects, the shape of which is divided into certain components and adjacent to each other, the front parts of which do not lie in the same plane;

3. When a generalized view of an object in the form of a simple geometric figure with holes, cutouts and grooves that do not violate the contour of its projections, it is recommended to use the method of "successive cutting out of parts";

4. It is recommended to use the "combined" method when performing axonometric images of objects with grooves, notches, notches and protrusions at the same time.

Images that have the basic features of an axonometric projection or a perspective image, without the use of drawing tools, visually approximate, respecting the proportions of the object, showing the ratio of light and shadow, are called technical drawings. Technical drawings have long been widely used as a means of depicting people's creative ideas on paper. Examples of the first technical drawings that have come down to us are pencil sketches by the great artist, engineer and scientist Leonardo da Vinci (1452-1519) (fig.).

When designing new models, products and structures, engineers, designers, architects use technical drawings as a means of expressing initial, intermediate and final options for technical solutions. In addition, technical drawings are used to verify the correct reading of the complex shape depicted in the drawing. Technical documentation is also included in export product documentation packages. They are used in product data sheets.

In the introductory part of the topic, the teacher should focus on the history and practical meaning of technical drawings like the ones above, then on the types of technical drawings (form), as well as on how to perform them (form). It is convenient to make technical drawings on checkered paper. The technical drawing of each object begins with the correct axonometric axis.

In the practice of performing technical drawings, the contour is not limited to the drawing. Several methods are used to bring out the size of the details, the clarity and content of the form. These methods are based on the ratio of light and shadow, which include hatching (dashed lines), gradation (dashed stripes) and dot hatching (fig.).

When shading, it is assumed that the light falls on the object from a height on the left. Light surfaces are not hatched, but shadow areas are hatched. The darker (shadow) the surface, the thicker the hatching should be.

Due to the fact that technical drafting skills are required in many areas, we found it necessary to provide the following additional recommendations:

In the expression of professional and human relations, ideas and projects, technical drawing skills are necessary for everyone. The main attention in mastering this type of drawing technique should be directed to the development of pencil skills. Learning how to draw with a pen or brush can be divided into optional classes.

First of all, it is necessary to work out exercises in the workbook that develop the skills of correct hand placement and visual acuity. Then draw the shapes chosen by the teacher, for example, flat shapes: a square, a right triangle (hexagon), a circle.

All drawings are done by hand on a sheet of white paper without drawing tools. The next task is to perform flat figures in axonometry (figures).

On the recommendation of the teacher, drawings of geometric objects are made in rectangular isometric or curvilinear frontal dimetric projections.

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GEOGRAFIYA FANINI O‘QITISHDA PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARNING AHAMIYATI

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26-maktabning geografiya fani o‘qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktab geografiya fanini o‘qitishda qo‘llaniladigan pedagogik texnologiya va metodlar haqida so‘z yuritiladi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются педагогические технологии и методы, используемые при обучении географии в школе.

Abstract: This article discusses the pedagogical technologies and methods used in teaching school geography.

Pedagogik texnologiyalarning eng asosiy negizi – bu o‘qituvchi va o‘quvchining belgilangan maqsaddan kafolatlangan natijaga hamkorlikda erishishlari uchun tanlangan texnologiyalarga bog‘liqdir [3, 6-b]. Har bir dars, mavzu, o‘quv predmetining o‘ziga xos texnologiyasi bor, ya‘ni o‘quv jarayonidagi pedagogik texnologiya – bu yakka tartibdagi jarayon bo‘lib, u o‘qituvchi va o‘quvchining ehtiyojidan kelib chiqqan holda bir maqsadga yo‘naltirilgan, oldindan loyihalashtirilgan va kafolatlangan natija berishga qaratilgan pedagogik jarayondir. Ta‘limda har qanday pedagogik texnologiyalar va metodlarning natijaviyligi uni qo‘llayotgan o‘qituvchining ijodiy va kasbiy mahoratiga bog‘liqdir.

Yaqin yillarda Milliy o‘quv dasturi asosida amalga oshiriladigan ta‘lim islohotlarida geografiya fani bo‘yicha amalga oshiriladigan ishlarning barchasi zamonaviy ta‘lim berishga qaratilgan.

Yuqoridagi fikrlardan kelib chiqqan holda maktab geografiya ta‘limining “Jahon iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy geografiyasi” fani mavzulari asosida yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarga asoslangan quydagi misollarni ko‘rishimiz mumkin.

1. “Kommunikativ suhbat” texnologiyasi. Geografiya ta‘limida bu texnologiyani foydalanish yaxshi samara beradi. Bunda o‘qituvchidan o‘quv

jarayoniga ijodiy yondashish, suhbat texnologiyasi usullaridan foydalana bilish, suhbat uchun savol va topshiriqlar tizimini ishlan chiqish, o'quvchilar o'rtasida munozaralarni ishlan chiqish talab qilinadi. “Jahon aholisi” bobining “Jahon aholisining soni, o'sishi va joylashuvi” mavzusida ushbu texnologiyani quydagicha qo'llash mumkin. Buning uchun sinf doskasiga A1 formatdagi vatman joylashtiriladi, uning chap qismiga mavzu bo'yicha vazifalar joylashtiriladi va o'ng tomoniga vazifaning yechimi yoziladi. O'quvchilar o'zlari uchun berilgan kartochkalarga ham suhbat, ham yozma tarzda chizmaga joylashtiriladi (1-rasm).

Nima uchun hozirgi kunda Afrikada demografik portlash yuzaga keldi?	• ? • ?
Nima uchun rivojlangan mamlakatlarda aholining umr surish davri uzoq davom etadi?	• ? • ?
Nima uchun suv bo'yida aholi zichligi yuqori bo'ladi?	• ? • ?

1-rasm. “Kommunikativ-suhbat” texnologiyasi.

2. “Geoklaster” metodi. Mazkur texnologiya 9-sinf “Jahon iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy geografiyasi” fani “Jahon aholisi” bobining “Amaliy mashg'ulot” mavzusida qo'llaniladi. Bu mavzu “Jahon aholisi” bobining eng so'nggi mavzusi hisoblanganligi uchun “Amaliy mashg'ulot” mavzusida “Jahonning demografik muammolari” deb nomlandi. Ushbu texnologiyaning nomi “Geoklaster” deyilishiga sabab, texnologiyani qo'llashda uning tarmoqlanadigan ko'rinishda tasvirlanishi, ushbu chizmalar ichiga mavjud muammolarning yozilishini hisobga olib, ramziy ma'noda “Geoklaster” deb nomlangan. Mazkur texnologiya orqali o'quvchilar demografik muammolarni o'rganish, balki muammolarni tahlil qilish barobarida ularning yechimini topadi va taqdimotini o'tkazadi (2-rasm).

2-rasm. “Geoklaster” metodi.

Ushbu texnologiyani o‘tkazish 3-bosqichdan iborat.

1-bosqich. O‘quvchilar zamonaviy demografik muammolarni berilgan chizmasining yoniga yozib boradilar.

2-bosqich: Berilgan muammolarni echimi o‘qituvchi tomonidan berilgan tarqatmaga o‘quvchi tomonidan individual tarzda yoziladi. Har bir o‘quvchi o‘ziga berilgan kartochkadagi muammolar yechimining taqdimotini qiladi hamda yuqoridagi muammolarga o‘z fikrini bildiradi.

3-bosqich: Yuqoridagi muammolarning yechimi yozilgan kartochkalarni o‘qituvchi tomonidan doskadagi chizmaning, klasterning ustiga yopishtirilib, tarmoqlar hosil qilinadi. Bu bu tarmoqlarning kengayib borishi kartochkadagi muammolar yechimining variativligi va taqdimot etilgan kartochkalar soniga bog‘liq bo‘ladi.

Ushbu texnologiyani qo‘llash orqali o‘quvchilar mavzuda berilgan zamonaviy demografik muammolar bilan mukammal tanishadi, muammolarning yechimini topishga harakat qiladi. Texnologiya orqali o‘qituvchi o‘quvchilarda bilim, ko‘nikma, malaka va kompetensiyalarni shakllanishiga erishadi. Shuningdek, o‘quvchilar mazkur texnologiya orqali muammoli vaziyatni anglash, uni hal etish, mantiqan dalillash, muammoni hal etish usullarini mantiqiy ketma-ketligini tushunish, o‘z javoblarining to‘g‘riligini dalillash va tekshirib qo‘rish imkoniga ega bo‘ladilar. “Geoklaster” texnologiyasini nafaqat demografik muammolar mavzusi, balki “Jahonning siyosiy xaritasi”, “Jahon davlatlarining siyosiy tuzumi va boshqaruvi”, “Jahon sanoati”, “Jahon qishloq xo‘jaligi”, “Jahon

transporti”, “Xalqaro iqtisodiy aloqalar” hamda fanning regional qismida jahon mamlakatlarining geografiyasi bo'yicha ham qo'llash maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Ushbu yaratilgan texnologiyadan nafaqat dars jarayonida, balki tadbirlarda, sinfdan tashqari ishlar va to'garak mashg'ulotlarida ham foydalanish mumkin.

3. “Raqamlar piramidasi” metodi. Ushbu texnologiyaning “Jahon aholisining etnik va diniy tarkibi” mavzusi misolida qo'llanildi (3-rasm).

“Raqamlar piramidasi” texnologiyasini qo'llashdan avval o'qituvchi butun dars davomida mavzu asosida o'tilgan raqamli ma'lumotlarni qo'lidagi maxsus qog'ozchaga yozib boradi. O'quvchilar darsning mustahkamlash qismida ushbu chizmaning ichiga qog'ozchalarni joylashtirishlari kerak bo'ladi.

“Raqamlar piramidasi” texnologiyasini qo'llash natijasida o'quvchilar sanoat tarmoqlarini qay darajada to'liq o'zlashtirganliklari aniqlanadi. Ushbu texnologiyadan nafaqat “Jahon aholisi” bobida, balki darslikning raqamlar mavjud bo'lgan barcha mavzulari bo'yicha ham qo'llash maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

Geografiya ta'limi texnologiyalarini qo'llash juda katta imkoniyatlarga ega, ammo mazkur texnologiyalarni qo'llash bo'yicha ilmiy-metodik ishlar endi rivojlanmoqda.

O'quvchilar “Raqamlar piramidasi”ni quydagicha to'ldirishi mumkin

3-rasm. “Raqamlar piramidasi” metodi.

4. “Geo-7” metodi. Ushbu “Geo-7” metodini qo'llash uchun “Jahon aholisi” bobining yakuni va umumlashtiruvchi darslar uchun tanlandi. “Geo-7” metodini qo'llashning mazmuni shundan iboratki, o'quvchilarga

fan bo'yicha reyting usulidagi 7 ta vazifa beriladi. Savollarga javob berish jarayonini dars sharoitidan kelib chiqib, og'zaki yoki yozma tarzda o'tkazish mumkin.

4-rasm. “Geo-7” metodi.

Savollar quyidagicha:

- 1). Aholisi eng ko'p bo'lgan 7 ta davlatni toping;
- 2). Aholisi tez o'sayotgan 7 ta davlatni aniqlang;
- 3). Aholisining o'sishi past 7 ta davlatni aniqlang;
- 4). Aholisining zichligi yuqori bo'lgan 7 ta davlatni toping;
- 5). Aholisining zichligi kam bo'lgan 7 ta davlatni toping;
- 6). Dunyodagi 7 ta aralash irqni aniqlang;
- 7). Yevropoid irqiga mansub 7 ta millatni yozing;
- 8). Mutloq soni eng ko'p bo'lgan 7 ta millatni yozing;
- 9). Jahondagi 7 ta dini toping;
- 10). Atlas asosida Oltoy til oilasiga mansub 7 ta filni yozing;
- 11). Soxta urbanizatsiya ko'p bo'lgan 7 ta davlatni toping;

“Geo-7” metodini “Jahon iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy geografiyasi” fanining barcha bo'limlari yakunidagina emas, mavzularni mustahkamlashda ham foydalanish mumkin bo'ladi (4-rasm).

5. “Georotatsiya” metodi. Ushbu so'zning ma'nosi “aylanma”, “harakat” degan ma'noda ifodalaniib, biror narsani tanlash va o'zaro bog'liqlikni aniqlash maqsadida qo'llaniladi (5-rasm).

5-rasm. Georotatsiya metodi.

Grafik organayzerda Jahon mamlakatlarning tillari ko'rsatilgan bo'lib, qaysi davlatda qaysi til tarqalganligini topish kerak. Ma'lumotlar bir-biriga chiziq orqali bog'lanadi.

6. “Ortiqchasi qaysi” metodi. “Jahon iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy geografiyasi” fanini o‘qitishda “Ortiqchasi qaysi” metodi ishlab chiqildi. metodni qo‘llashda “Jahon aholisining etnik va diniy tarkibi” mavzusi misolida ko‘rib chiqildi. Metodning organayzerida berilgan ma‘lum mavzuga tegishli ma‘lumotlarning to‘rttasini va tegishli bo‘lmagan bitta ortiqcha ma‘lumotni o‘quvchilar aniqlashi lozim bo‘ladi. Masalan, 4 ta din berilgan bo‘lsa, uning 3 tasi dunyoviy din hisoblanadi va bittasi ortiqcha (6-rasm).

Dunyoviy dinlar

Ko‘p millatli davlatlar

Eng ko‘p millatlar

Bir millatli davlatlar

6-rasm. “Ortiqchasi qaysi” metodi.

Bu metodni qo'llash natijasida o'quvchilarda mustaqil fikrlashi takomillashadi. O'z fikrini erkin bayon eta oladi. O'rganilayotgan geografik materiallarning samaradorlik haqidagi ma'lumotlarning ishonchliligini oshiradi va o'quv jarayonini boshqarish imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Bu metodni darsda ham elektron, ham qog'oz variantda qo'llasa bo'ladi. “Ortiqchasi qaysi” metodini “Jahon iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy geografiyasi” fanining barcha mavzularida qo'llash mumkin.

7. “Venn diagrammasi” metodi. Ushbu metod diagramma-grafik ko'rinishda bo'lib, olingan natijalarni umumlashtirib, ulardan bir butun xulosa chiqarishga, ikki va undan ortiq predmetni tahlil qilish va o'rganishda qo'llaniladi. Diagramma ikki va undan ortiq aylananing kesishmasidan hosil bo'ladi (7-rasm).

Bu diagrammani qo'llashdan maqsad ikki va undan ortiq predmet va tushunchalarni taqqoslashda, turli va umumiy tomonlarini aniqlashda bilim va ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishdan iborat.

Aytaylik “Jahon mamlakatlarining urbanizatsiyasi” mavzusida mazkur diagrammani qo'llash mumkin. Diagrammaning ikki qismiga “Urbanizatsiyaning ijobiy jihatlari” va “Urbanizatsiyaning salbiy jihatlari” mavzulari yoziladi. O'quvchilar shu asosida diagrammani to'ldiradilar.

7-rasm. “Venn diagrammasi” metodi.

Amalga oshirish bosqichlari:

1-bosqich. O‘quvchilar ikki guruhga bo‘linadi. Birinchi guruh “Urbanizatsiyaning ijobiy jihatlari”ni ikkinchi guruh esa “Urbanizatsiyaning salbiy jihatlari”ni qismini to‘ldiradi.

2-bosqich. Ikki guruhga bo‘lingan o‘quvchilar birlashib doiraning o‘rta qismiga ikki mavzuning o‘xshashlik tomonlarini yozadi.

3-bosqich. Kichik guruhlarda bu xulosalarning umumiy hossalarni aniqlashni taklif etamiz.

4-bosqich. Biron bir guruh vakili har bir tushunchaning o‘ziga xos tomonlarini o‘qiydi. Boshqalar zarurat tug‘ilganda uning javobini to‘ldiradilar.

5-bosqich. Boshqa guruh vakillari ikki tushunchani birlashtiruvchi xususiyatlarni o‘qiydi. Boshqalar zarurat tug‘ilganda uning javobini to‘ldiradilar.

Umuman olganda “Venn diagrammasi”ni geografiya uchun yaratilgan metod deyish mumkin.

Yuqorida ishlab chiqilgan va yangicha ko‘rinish kasb etgan interfaol metodlar va o‘yinlar mavzuning mazmun mohiyatini maktab o‘quvchilari ongiga tezroq, soddaroq va amaliy jihatdan asoslab berish maqsadida ishlab chiqilgan.

Natijada, “Jahon iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy geografiyasi” fanini o‘qitishda yaratilgan multimedia ilovalari, pedagogik texnologiyalar, takomillashtirilgan interfaol metodlar va o‘yinlar orqali o‘quvchilarning bilish faoliyatini faollashtirish hamda takomillashtirish, ularni ma’naviy-ahloqiy intellektual jihatdan rivojlantirish, bu jarayonni bir-biriga uyg‘unlashtirish, faoliyatning natijasini hamjihatlikda tahlil qilishga imkon beradi.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF INCREASING THE ACTIVITY AND MOTIVATION OF FUTURE VOCATIONAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation. This article presents a number of ideas as mechanisms for increasing the activity of students in the field of vocational education, as well as the purpose, content, types of educational activities of students, the diversity of the educational process in which they are involved, student activity, independence, cognitive activity as a process has an imitative, reproductive, exploratory, creative nature, the content of the organization of educational activities, the result, the content and analysis of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

Keywords: education, process, profession, student, activity, activity, motive, quality, result, formation.

Today, the work on radical improvement of the education system in our country, the creation of a strong organizational and legal mechanism for the development of worthy successors of our future is gaining momentum. The pace of global development, like all other spheres, requires a new approach to the educational process, the introduction of innovative technologies. Accordingly, educating the younger generation to be physically healthy, intellectually developed, independent-minded, strong-willed, loyal to the motherland, deepen democratic reforms and increase their social activity in the development of civil society are important tasks. Consequently, the development of any state and society is inextricably linked with the maturity, aspirations and courage of the younger generation. In this regard, the steady increase in investments from the state budget in the social sphere, including the reform of the education system, the training of highly qualified personnel in the field of education laws and state programs, ensuring the effective integration of science and industry, educating young people in the spirit of national and universal values. the success of the tasks is particularly noteworthy.

The state policy in the field of training is based on the formation of a comprehensively developed person - a citizen through a system of continuous education, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual and spiritual and moral upbringing of man. Therefore, one of the main requirements for the teacher is to form in students the motivation to study.

It is well known that motivation is a psychological factor that is the source, cause, evidence, and various possibilities of student activity. It is a powerful tool that encourages students to work hard to learn the basics of knowledge, skills, specialties with enthusiasm and interest. That is, motivation is the purposeful orientation of students in psychological (spiritual) ways to increase their activity in learning. It is related to the satisfaction of a specific need [1]. And need is manifested in causes, because need is a motive that drives people to action. At the same time, there is a need to shape the need for students to acquire knowledge. The task of the teacher is, on the one hand, to find ways to form the need for knowledge in students, to find and apply them in the learning process, and on the other hand, to improve and coordinate the activities to meet the need for knowledge. In order to increase the activity of students in the process of acquiring knowledge, it is expedient to form the inclinations, interests and needs.

Although the activity of students in higher education institutions seems to represent two separate process states, it is an indicator of the behavior that occurs in a holistic, whole process based on the mutual integration between them [2]. The emergence of activity in students, on the one hand, represents the effectiveness of education, as well as the result of pedagogical activities aimed at its formation. The formation of student activity in higher education institutions also indicates the training of a qualified specialist in the conditions of market relations.

It is known that the subject of educational activity in higher education institutions is a student. Therefore, in the center of education with a socio-pedagogical basis lies its personality, consciousness, as well as the relationship between the world under study and its partners in educational activities: students, teachers who organize and direct their education. This issue has been equally important at all times.

The activity of the student is reflected in his intellectual reflection in the process of learning, in the performance of general and individual tasks [3]. These features not only ensure that students receive a high level of knowledge, but also are characteristic of his vital activity, that is, the formation of the student's personality, his active attitude to practice, to life. Therefore, it is safe to say that the development of learning activity is the formation of an active life outlook of the individual.

Another distinctive aspect of the educational activity of students of higher education institutions is that it has a specific organizational content. As the purpose, content and types of educational activities of students are included in the program, the educational process in which they are

involved is different; subject (student) power can go with activity, independence, different spending. In some cases, students' learning activities as a process can be simulated, reproductive (productive), exploratory, creative in nature. The content of the organization of educational activities affects the final result - the nature of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities [4, 5, 6].

The following can be considered as mechanisms to increase the activity of students in the acquisition of knowledge:

1) the training sessions should be organized in such a way that they allow the teacher to communicate more with each other;

2) it is important to be able to answer questions of interest to students on the topic without delaying the end of the lesson, even if the question is not directly related to the topic;

3) to appreciate and encourage any achievements of students in reading and learning;

4) not to misinterpret the answers and to create conditions for the student to fully use their abilities, to demonstrate their knowledge;

5) develop their initiative and encourage it by available means;

6) prevent students from remaining in a passive observer position when using technical means of teaching, effective use of modern, interactive methods of teaching;

7) Strict adherence to the principle of fairness in the assessment of students' knowledge. Unless students are rewarded for their hard work and ability, their intellectual intelligence, they will not try to acquire active knowledge.

8) to convey the content of education in the volume and complexity that students receive at the level of mental ability;

9) the position of the teacher: - hardship, rigidity, if necessary, negligence (to some shortcomings of the student), relative impartiality, demanding, cheerful, professional knowledge, pedagogical ability. On the contrary, arrogance, nervousness, lowering of rating points, paperwork, excessive exhortation, dissatisfaction with the deans lead to nervousness of students and increase their stubbornness, leading to a decrease in their activity in education. The complexity of the teacher's work lies in the fact that he is able to find a way to the heart of each student, to create conditions for the development of opportunities in each individual [7, 8, 9, 10].

Nowadays, curricula start with a short practical knowledge and then suddenly with practical training. In fact, it would be right to move on to

practical training only if you know the theory well. Only then will students have a desire to expand and deepen their knowledge.

In order to increase students' interest in learning, the existing problems should be studied, divided into groups by specialization, brought to the attention of students with proposals for solutions on specific topics, ways to motivate students who have found a significant solution to the problem. This method also helps to increase students' interest and activity in reading [11].

The teacher must know the latest scientific ideas, scientific achievements. If each time the new source of information is the students themselves, and the teacher is dragged down by the events, soon there will be a trace of his pedagogical and educational influence [12]. The teacher's broad outlook, ability to find satisfactory answers to any question, ability to comment on the news, instills in students a sense of respect for him and the science he teaches. Involving students in the teacher's learning process, finding common ground, discussing various issues among all students, and approaching issues of ethics and behavioral culture correctly will also help to increase students' learning activity.

In conclusion, in order to increase the activity of students in the acquisition of knowledge, the teacher should have a wide range of knowledge in their field, conduct lessons based on interesting examples, instructive stories, life experiences and conclusions, take into account the interests of students during the lesson. will have to try to find answers to the questions. Also, the effective use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the widespread use of modern technical means of lessons, handouts will further improve the learning process of students. Each subject has its own aspects, of course, that attract students. There are many such aspects, especially in the specialty sciences, in our opinion. In order to increase the educational activity of students in specialized disciplines, the role of the studied science in human life and development, its role in the economy and potential of the country should be very well covered. Only then will the student try to study the subject in more depth.

Hence, the quality and effectiveness of the educational process is directly based on the interaction of teachers and students. Therefore, the teacher's main focus should be on the formation of learning motives in students.

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THE INTERRELATIONSHIP IN THE PSYCHE OF THE EDUCATOR AND THE LEARNER

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Annotation. The article is aimed at increasing the intellectual potential of students in the educational process and the processes related to the development of human mental activity and the psyche of students, conscious understanding of the content of the educational process, intellectual development of students, improving existing skills, effective socialization, consistent work on themselves. , in the pursuit of professional maturity and the pursuit of theoretical ideas of creativity, humanism, the study of the growing interest of students in education, professional development in the presence of similar information.

Key words: education, student, upbringing, information, content, essence, activity, process, result.

The rapid penetration of innovations into the education system in our country, the determination of global information in modern conditions, encourages every student to have a large amount of information. Today's young people need to be educated in the conditions of similar information in their personal development, intellectual development, development of existing abilities, effective socialization, consistent work on themselves, professional development and the pursuit of theoretical ideas of creativity, humanism. promotes an increase in interest in perfection.

The educational process includes the components of the educational process, including teaching and the tools used, methods of teaching to solve specific goals and objectives, the participation of independent learners and educators in this process, as well as visual and technical aids [1].

The educational process, the continuity and continuity between the teacher and the learner, that is, the connection is an important component of the pedagogical process. At the same time it is always necessary to pay attention to the following ideas of the reading process:

- Reading is a direct process through which learners receive new information throughout their lives;

- There is a lack of teaching children to read, they need to be taught to read thoughtfully, and as a result, students will have a new idea and will be able to enter the scientific community;
- Reading is not just a science of learning, but a tool for thinking and knowing the world;
- Reading and response to reading is a key way of critical analysis;
- The study of different subjects usually requires a lot of independent reading from the learner, so understanding the reading process can improve the mastery and analysis of what is read in a particular subject [2, 3, 4].

This means that the state of the learner in the educational process will also be a solid didactic basis for achieving optimal options for activities in this area. In this regard, the intellectual potential, mental and physiological health of the learner and their sense of joy are very important in the educational process.

“A student's sense of joy is an important spiritual product in creating a successful environment for them to complete learning tasks in the classroom.

This is one of the main aspects of the educational process, in which one of the most effective ways to stimulate the desire to read is realized, and in them a sense of joy is realized.

It is well known that a learner cannot fully believe in subsequent successes unless he or she experiences the joys of success. Therefore, experienced teachers choose tasks for learners in such a way that they become easy tasks to solve at the appropriate stage. It uses two types of tasks, one of which is easily completed by the learner, and creates an aspiration base to solve another relatively more complex task. The success base is created by stratifying tasks of the same complexity. Choosing a comfortable spiritual environment to complete the learning tasks plays an important role in creating a situation of success. A comfortable micro-social environment eliminates feelings of mutual insecurity, fear or apprehension while reading. In this case, the state of hesitation is replaced by a state of confidence [5, 6].

The technology of educational play activities is also important in ensuring the connection between the educational process and its participants. Such technology is more similar to stratified learning technology, in that the learning game becomes meaningful when the educator and learner interact. To do this, the project of the training game should be developed in advance and the assessment of the planned results should be determined in advance, as well as the training tasks should be

clearly defined, methodological methods and possibilities of overcoming a complex situation should be identified.

When conducting educational work in order to organize the learning activities of learners, the educator must not forget that he must first solve three tasks through the learning process, that is, three goals through teaching. These goals combine the activities of educators and learners.

1. The educational purpose is to know the content of educational materials, that is, to be able to master and apply scientific knowledge related to this subject.

2. The educational goal is to form one's own personal qualities, beliefs under the influence of the ideas and worldviews that lie in its content by mastering the basics of science.

3. The developmental goal is to develop a person's mental maturity, cognitive abilities, attitude to study, work under the influence of the educational process [7, 8, 9].

As a result of achieving these goals, the learner develops the ability to work independently, teaches him to think, thinking dominates the learning process.

Modernity in education - the idea of a national program is the obligation to introduce scientifically based and tested didactic innovations, active methods and forms, procedures in educational practice. The level of development of education is characterized by scientific and technical innovations included in its content.

The development of the intellectual sphere in education is the process of developing students' thinking (knowledge, creativity), memory, attention, mental qualities (depth, flexibility, thrift, independence), thinking skills, learning skills, subject knowledge, learning and skills.

Development of willpower in education is a process of formation of goal-orientation in the learner, in which to overcome the tension of nerves and muscles, initiative, self-confidence, self-management, knowledge (how to operate), activity development, how to implement it and external control. skills such as incompetence are important.

The development of the motivational sphere in education is the process of shaping the learner's needs for intellectual knowledge, understanding of nature, society, human thinking and the laws of cognition.

The development of the emotional sphere in education is a process of developing in the learner the necessary skills to manage their emotions and mental states, in which it is important to cultivate the ability to overcome excessive anxiety and self-assessment.

In general, the educational process consists of 4 main stages:

1. Understand the material to be mastered.
2. The formation of the concept of choosing it.
3. Development of skills and competencies to strengthen and improve knowledge.
4. Apply the acquired skills and abilities in practice.

Each stage is characterized by a specific description of the learners' cognitive activity. This activity requires special guidance from the educator [10].

The essence of the knowledge acquired at the initial stage of the learning process is understood using the methods of analysis and synthesis.

Analysis (breaking into pieces) - is the division of things, events and happenings into components, pieces. For example, pomegranate is divided into hard skin, layers - layers and grains.

Synthesis is the process of thinking that is the opposite of analysis. What is being studied in it is the unification of the individual parts of events and happenings as a whole.

Learners' thinking activities are also reflected in comparisons.

Comparison is an operation of thinking aimed at finding differences and similarities, equality and inequality in things and events.

Inductive and deductive thinking are important in understanding the learning material.

Inductive reasoning (inference) is a method of logical cognition, one of the forms of thinking, based on inference, which goes from the individual or individual cases to the general, from some facts to generalizations.

Deductive inference (division, inference) is a method of drawing logical conclusions from general judgments to specific judgments, one of the forms of thinking.

Concepts are formed in learners based on the use of methods of analysis, synthesis, comparison, inductive reasoning and deductive reasoning.

Concept is a form of thinking in which the object of reality is the expression of important signs and features of events in a single word or combination of words. As the learning process takes on a dialectical character, the concepts gradually deepen and become more complex.

The assimilation of information, the formation of concepts, the assimilation of knowledge is an important situation in the overall process. The inability to reflect on the material studied, the inability to be independent in

its educational and labor activities, and the lack of a creative approach to them lead to the superficial assimilation of knowledge.

We believe that the structural structure, which allows us to study the legal relationship between the educational process and social systems and conditions, is the leading methodological resource, the basis for us to study the laws of education. Then the relationship between teaching and learning processes, which are part of education, and, finally, the tasks and content of the learning process are considered.

The components of the educational process are: purposefulness, motivational - explanatory, content, operational activities (methods, forms of education), control, correction, assessment, outcome assessment. The components of the educational process reflect the development of interactions between educators and learners, from goal setting to setting goals and achieving tangible results. At the same time, these components of the educational process should take into account the established periodic cooperation of educators and learners.

In conclusion, effective ways of implementing the educational process are achieved through an integral link between the educator and the learner. For this reason, feedback in the learning process and its management is a key tool for learners to understand the learning material. Here, feedback is extremely important in ensuring that the educator and learner are moving towards the intended goal and adjusting the process as needed. It guarantees the selection of the optimal option to achieve the planned goal. Through this, learners understand the essence of the learning material, find optimal solutions, ideas and laws known in pedagogical practice, as well as learners improve their intellectual potential.

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FORMATION OF INDEPENDENT CREATIVE WORK ACTIVITIES IN STUDENTS

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Annotation. In the article the student realizes, perceives, perceives, imagines and remembers the correctness, accuracy, authenticity, validity or relevance of the events and phenomena that he reflects, perceives, assumes, assumes in the process of independent thinking. generalize, understand the internal, complex connections, relationships, properties, characteristics and mechanisms between things and events, the student to predict the emergence, development and consequences of natural and social phenomena and events based on certain laws, laws and regulations the formation of abilities, the importance of independent thinking in the rational, efficient organization of the student's cognitive and practical activities are analyzed in detail.

Key words: student, education, system, process, creation, research, thinking, perception, imagination, understanding, hypothesis, conclusion, formation.

In the process of education, great attention is paid to the fact that they do not discriminate against any stratum of society, to develop personnel who can think independently and creatively. One of the urgent tasks is to develop the aptitude, abilities, knowledge and skills of young people, to teach general subjects for them to take up their chosen professions, to effectively organize their independent and creative work, to provide this process with new teaching materials.

We need specialists with well-developed thinking and independent thinking in various fields. It is a modern requirement that the study of independent thinking of students should be a priority in the educational process. Throughout a child's life, independent thinking at all stages of education should remain a basic requirement. Thinking or reasoning is the highest form of student mental activity, intellectual intelligence, rhythm of behavior, conscious behavior. Independent thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social environment and reality, as well as the main condition for the rational, efficient implementation of a wide range of intellectual activities of the student. In the realization of independent thinking, the student develops ideas, reflections, ideas, hypotheses, goals, etc., and they

are expressed in the mind of the person as concepts, judgments, conclusions. Independent thinking manifests itself in close connection with language and speech, and they are continuously interdependent. For the same reason, the student is radically different from the beings in existence due to his independent thinking (communication), speech, and conscious behavior.

Typically, thinking is divided into several types depending on the degree of generalization of reality, the nature of the problem-solving tool, the novelty of the object for the student and its motivation for activity [1]. When analyzing independent thinking as a mental activity, it involves the solution of problems and tasks by the student, observed in their conditions, essence, structure, forms and possibilities of understanding and comprehension of the individual. Problem, problem, task solving (solving, execution) is considered in connection with the student's needs, interests, inclinations, motivations, mental abilities, talents, potentials, accepting the requirements of the problem, making personal decisions, searching for solutions, form a solid foundation for research and thinking. In independent and creative thinking activities, the management of the problem-solving process, the student's emotions, inner experiences, emergencies, objective conditions are of special importance for him in the perception of existence.

In social life in the system of higher education, in the practice of production, the rhythm of interpersonal (objective, subjective) relations, connections, the result of joint mental and physical labor occurs as a complex of non-standard thinking. Qualities of independent thinking in the student community include criticism and self-criticism, assessment and self-assessment, review and self-monitoring, management and self-governance, self-development, self-expression, self-command, group reflection and personal observation formed [2].

Human perception of a person, i.e., determining the mental state of a stranger, guessing him, collecting materials about the most necessary signs and symptoms, is also a product of creative thinking. This complex stage-by-stage process of cognition requires volitional effort, mental seriousness, conscious attitude, a stable situation, favorable conditions, through the direct influence of which a certain decision is made.

Creative works, discoveries, inventions, inventive proposals are also the product of creative thinking, and its tasks include scientific assumptions, ideas, glorious goals, lofty noble intentions of practical and theoretical significance [3].

Student thinking activity is social in nature. During the period of social and historical development of thinking, there was a need to exchange ideas and share experiences, first in search of food for food, and then in the creation and use of tools of labor. As a result of human interaction, interaction, and communication, the ability to express opinions and speak has begun to emerge. Thanks to the speech, the consistency, logic, systematization of the products of thinking has emerged, which has the opportunity to leave as a traditional legacy for future generations. Had the systematized experience, knowledge, skills and abilities accumulated by mankind not been left behind, human thinking would not have been able to achieve such great achievements in the fields of science, technology and culture [4, 5, 6].

In the activity of independent thinking, the student determines the accuracy, precision, authenticity, truthfulness of the things and events that he reflects, perceives, perceives, imagines, remembers, or whether they fall into reality (appropriate) and do not understand. Judgments, concepts, conclusions, hypotheses (assumptions) formed in the process of knowing existence determine whether decisions are true or not. The student, through independent thinking, indirectly or indirectly reflects the reality, generalizes, understands the internal, complex connections, relationships, properties, features and mechanisms between things and events. Consequently, the student has the opportunity to predict the occurrence, course, development of natural and social phenomena and events, as well as their consequences, based on certain laws, laws and regulations. The importance of independent thinking is especially important in the rational, efficient organization of cognitive and practical activities of modern students.

Independent thinking in a student begins with the emergence of a problematic situation, but the emergence of this situation, the solution does not end there [7]. The tendency of the student to know, involuntary behavior does not shine until the problem situation, it occurs vaguely, then a problem situation in need of a solution is created in this sense, and finally its solution is found, but the post-problem stage of cognition continues involuntarily in its direction [8].

In the student's learning activity there is a tightly interconnected chain of thinking: independent thinking, problem, issue (assignment).

Student independent thinking can be structured in the following stages.

1. In the activity of independent thinking, first of all, the problem (task) that needs to be solved should be identified by the student. If there is no

issue or problem in front of him, then he does not even think about anything. This means that the student is not confronted with any problem, the easier and more complete the information he has to solve, the easier it will be for him to find a way and means to do it wisely. To do this, students must first understand the content of the issue to a certain extent, check its conditions, determine what is known and what is unknown. Only in this way will they not be in a hurry and will be able to search for the condition without hesitation (task), analyze it with their minds, and solve it correctly.

2. Strive to apply all the knowledge (rules, factors, laws, properties, attributes, important features, relationships, connections, etc.) that is most necessary to solve a problem or issue. To do this, the process of transfer to a new environment, the object, using the situations encountered in the personal experience of the student, effective methods.

3. Hypothesis (hypothesis) related to the problem or problem is put forward, the stages are analyzed, the solution is considered, various options and variations, invariants are expressed, which are divided into the most effective signs, symbols, etc. as a result of mutual comparison.

4. It is necessary to test the hypothesis of the problem with the help of the results of certain criteria. To examine it, the cases of mutual similarity are compared in spiritual, formal, structural terms. In this case, the materials of creative imagination are used in detail, that is, to make creative plans, to create generalized images, to visualize the results, to understand the hypothetical relationships. To ensure that it is valid, a system of mental behaviors is applied and the intention to make some changes is clarified. The hypothesis is analyzed and synthesized using logical methods, its important features are distinguished, and quick judgments and conclusions are made on its correctness and validity.

5. If it is determined that the hypothesis put forward to solve the problem theoretically is correct or incorrect, it is squeezed out of the object of reasoning and new hypotheses, ideas are found. The new practical hypothesis idea is tested several times and then it is recommended to try it to put it into practice. Most of the considerations are analyzed in the solution of constructive technical problems, inventions, inventions, rationalizations, introduction of technological devices, various models, options, drugs, technological maps, etc. the fit is selected and the head-scratching on it is continued.

6. To solve a problem or issue, to solve it, to create confidence and satisfaction in the correctness of the results obtained, the student completes the independent thinking behavior by examining it. It is these mental

operations, after the forms of reflection, that the problem (task) is found to be completely solved, and thinking about it is relatively stopped.

The student's independent thinking can consist of the following stages:

1. The emergence of the problem in the field of student perception.
2. Understanding of the essence of the problem, problem, assignment by the student.
3. The emergence of similar data or images.
4. Decrease in imagination and memory materials, continuous birth of assumptions.
5. Step-by-step verification of assumptions or confirmation of their validity.
6. The emergence and improvement of new assumptions.
7. Secondary test of assumptions (second confirmation)
8. Problem, task, problem solving (Solution).
9. Continuation of involuntary mental behavior (relative duration of thoughts), etc.

In order to teach students to think independently, it is advisable to pay attention to the following, taking into account the spiritual, formal, structural aspects of the problem:

- One of the options of questions, which are expressed after the analysis of the problems, issues, assignments, connections between them, connections, relationships, the questions of which are not specified, are indicated in parentheses;

- Problems, issues, tasks, missing information for their solution (execution, solution) remain in parentheses;

- problem, issue, assignment with excess information, details;

- Problems, issues, tasks that can be solved, solved, performed in several ways, methods, step by step, where various issues (problems, tasks) are given, with the most convenient, simple, most economical, efficient way of solving as hidden as possible the transition of problems from one mode of thinking to another, from a simpler sentence to a more complex one, from one conclusion to its particular appearances and forms, will be aimed at shaping the student's mental ability;

- Problems, issues, tasks, the content and essence of which change, they also focus on the formation of mental abilities, consisting of the transition from one reinforced mental behavior to another, that is, they are taught to use them in the process of moving to a new situation;

- Problems, issues, tasks aimed at proving, discovering, discovering, with the help of which logical thinking improves mental abilities, such as proving internal relations, understanding the laws;

- Independent thinking, logical reasoning, problems, assignments, issues, no special knowledge is required to solve them, but it requires a certain level of creativity, appeal to life, the ability to think logically, some of which are mathematical. , others are referenced only in the form of logical puzzles.

Independent thinking, with its effectiveness, relevance, universality, professional training leads students to mastery, provides a solid foundation for understanding society and natural phenomena.

Independence of thinking means that the student is able to set a clear goal, new tasks on his own initiative, to make practical and theoretical, characteristic hypotheses (roughly, hypotheses) on them, to imagine the expected result, to solve the problem without anyone's help or guidance. due to his mental research, it is possible to understand the mental ability to find different ways, methods, means and solve them independently [9].

The independence of thought is manifested in the diligence, perseverance, and critique of the mind. The initiative of the mind means that the student sets a clear goal, a clear task for the new problem, to complete all this, to personally look for ways and means to find a solution, to make mental efforts, to introduce additional signs and symptoms. is held. The perseverance of the mind is expressed in the rapid solution of tasks, in the precise application of new methods and means in solving them, in the liberation from old ways, and in other mental processes.

The criticality of the mind is important in being able to examine one's own and others' opinions, whether these opinions are true or not, and to be able to evaluate the opinions, discussions, and problematic situations that have arisen. Such critique is called objective critique if it is based on a certain criterion for the correct disclosure of the essence of the problem to a reasonable, important character. A situation in which a student's critical thinking shifts to subjective (personal) errors in general to subjectivism is called subjective criticality. It is safe to say that if the critical thinking in the student's thinking is carried out rationally, fairly, efficiently, then both mental and moral qualities (qualities) that are important for the person will emerge.

The independence of a student's thinking is inextricably linked to his or her productivity. If a student for a certain period of time has made valuable and new ideas, ideas, recommendations for a particular field, and solved theoretical and practical tasks, such a person's thinking is called productive. serves as a criterion. Even when the student thinks of simple things, he is not

limited to their external signs, but seeks to reveal the essence of events, trying to create a general social law from the realities of ordinary life. Undoubtedly, the student's independent thinking has untapped and untapped potential, the full discovery of which serves the purpose of accelerating the development of science and technology. Any organization, innovation is the product of development-human intelligence, so the development of science and technology in many respects depends on the independent thinking of the specialist. Student maturity consists of physical, moral and mental stages, in which his independent thinking takes the lead, a priority. Although today's students easily reach the level of physical and moral perfection, but the achievement of mental maturity can be achieved gradually, thanks to the patterns of nervous system tension, mental tension, emotional seriousness, stable willpower, continuous activity, devotion. It is expedient to form in students independent thinking, creative research, methods of intellectual activity in order to acquire the spirituality and values created by our ancestors, as well as to ensure their future development.

At present, the form of organization of teaching in higher education does not fully form the ability to acquire and learn independently. This situation has a negative impact on the development of an independent and free-thinking person. There is also very little research on the development and activation of independent work and creative activity of young people.

The development of methods for the effective organization and conduct of independent work in higher education, the use of active methods aimed at the development of creative activities of students remains a requirement of the times.

In conclusion, the rapid development of science and technology, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication systems, the rapid renewal of knowledge in various fields, the daily changes in techniques and technologies allow for independent learning, the creation and implementation of electronic textbooks. requires the development of methodologies. The content of e-textbooks created in general professional subjects should be focused on the development of creative abilities of students, provide opportunities for independent learning, the formation of skills to search for new knowledge. Based on the above details and analysis, scientific research on the above-mentioned problems indicates that it is an urgent task today.

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INFORMATION SUPPORT AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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Annotation. The article aims to create an information learning environment, to introduce a systematic approach to its management, to define the purpose of the information-educational environment of the educational institution in accordance with the content of modern education at the initial stage of this approach. The purpose of modern education is to consist of a system of knowledge, skills and abilities formed in accordance with the requirements of the specialist model, the purpose of the electronic information-educational environment in higher pedagogical education, to develop in direct connection with the requirements of the student issues that are important in shaping student personality have been interpreted.

Key words: education, student, information, supply, process, management, mastery, aspiration, impact, quality, result, formation.

The current stage of education reform puts forward urgent tasks related to the speed of renewal in society, the rapid adaptation to new, higher requirements for educational institutions. In this context, the weight of measures aimed at developing the educational institution and ensuring that it operates at the level of modern requirements is constantly growing. Almost all of the tasks set are fundamentally new, and it is not enough for the team to work on the basis of existing experience alone. An analysis of research on the theory and practice of management of educational institutions shows that in modern conditions, the management of an educational institution remains directly related to the management of the exchange of information in it. This, in turn, shows that the improvement of the educational institution can be achieved through the effective use of information technology, and leads to the need for targeted research in this area.

The creation of an electronic information educational environment of the educational institution is not only a purely technical issue, but also requires the use of scientific, methodological, organizational and pedagogical capabilities of the institution on the basis of a systematic approach [1].

In our opinion, the concept of "electronic information-educational environment" can be defined as a set of software, information-technical, educational-methodical systems that provide a goal-oriented learning process [2, 3]. Electronic information-educational environment is characterized by the following typological features:

1. The electronic information-educational environment at any level is a complex structural object of a systemic nature.

2. The integrity of the electronic information-educational environment is synonymous with the concept of achieving systemicity, combining them with the educational goals in the implementation of the personal and professional model of the graduate of the educational institution.

3. The electronic information-educational environment is not only a factor influencing the effectiveness of educational work, but also a tool.

Alternatively, there are a number of differing views on the definition of an information-learning environment, including:

- an organized set of information, technical, educational and methodological support, which is inextricably linked with the individual as a subject of the educational environment;

- a single information educational environment based on the integration of electronic information carriers, virtual libraries, distributed databases, computers, educational and methodological complexes, information and communication technologies [4].

A systematic approach to creating and managing an information learning environment is required. In the first stage of this approach, the purpose of the information-educational environment of the educational institution is determined in accordance with the content of modern education [5]. In pedagogical activity, the purpose of education plays a systematic role. The clearly defined goal serves as a basis for choosing the content, purpose, organizational forms of education. The goal of modern education is a system of knowledge, skills and competencies that is formed in accordance with the requirements of the specialist model, which is reflected in the relevant educational standards [13]. In addition, the student's personality is not only the object of the pedagogical process, but also its subject. In such cases, the importance of the student's independent

learning increases and requires the formation of the following skills and competencies:

1. Skills and competencies for planning independent learning: developing an individual plan for independent activity; targeted activities based on a plan; monitor its activities and make necessary corrections.

2. Skills and abilities to use scientific and educational information on the Internet: independent identification of scientific and educational information; independent analysis and evaluation of new information; search and find sources of information on the Internet in terms of the problem to be solved; to be able to see new and promising news in the content of the received information.

3. Skills and abilities to work on electronic information and educational resources: systematic use of electronic manuals and catalogs; Be able to keep a list of scientific, educational and other literature obtained from the Internet in accordance with the rules of bibliography.

4. Skills and abilities to master the lectures presented by means of modern information technologies: to determine the topic and plan of lectures, the list of references; correct receipt of information provided; distinguish the main problem, idea and conclusion; write a summary of the main content in your own words; to process, store the information provided and use its content for educational purposes.

5. Skills and abilities to work with the electronic textbook: to get acquainted with the electronic textbook in general, to know its author, content, conclusion, illustrations and annotations; distinguish the logical structure of the electronic textbook; additional guides to fully understand the topic under study: animation, dictionary, encyclopedia, reference books; to record the received information in the form of abstracts, abstracts.

The e-learning environment has the following three main functions:

- to help the subjects of the external environment to form an idea of the information-educational environment of the educational institution with the help of modern information technologies;

- increase the interaction of the staff of the educational institution and create an environment for the exchange of information and educational resources;

- organization and management of effective information exchange in the educational institution through the means of information-educational environment [6, 7, 8, 9].

Defining the purpose of the information-educational environment in the educational institution is carried out taking into account the periodic

sequence of three processes: in the first period the results of the analysis of the environment are studied; in the second period - the measures to be taken accordingly are determined; in the third period the purpose of the information-educational environment of direct educational institution is developed [10, 11].

The purpose of the electronic information-educational environment in the higher pedagogical educational institution is developed in direct connection with the requirements to the future teacher [12]. In turn, in the formation of the personality of the future teacher, special attention is paid to the formation of qualities aimed at continuous self-development during post-graduate work. In this regard, it should be noted that the ongoing educational reforms in the country require a new interpretation of the concept of "profession". According to the requirements of the national model of training, a modern professional is characterized not only by a set of ready professional knowledge, but also by skills that contribute to professional development, the ability to analyze their professional level, readiness to acquire new knowledge in accordance with society and industry. The basis of the listed qualities is a developmental process aimed at the implementation of continuous professional training through the acquisition of new knowledge throughout life.

Thus, the organization and management of informatization of pedagogical educational processes requires the study of the electronic information-educational environment of pedagogical education, the creation of integrated information-educational resources as a factor in improving the quality of education.

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THE NEED TO ORGANIZE THE PROFESSIONAL CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation. The article deals with the existence of great pedagogical and psychological opportunities in the formation and development of personal creativity, the correct organization of theoretical research and practical activities in its realization, the diversity and complexity of the organization of professional creativity of future teachers. topical issues such as the readiness of future vocational education teachers, young professionals who have just started working in colleges to organize creative activities of students, the preparation of future vocational education teachers to lead creative activities of students in vocational colleges.

Key words: education, student, process, creativity, research, creation, observation, aspiration, ability, result, development.

Analysis of the activities of teachers of vocational education in higher education institutions shows that they need to develop professional competence in their subject and the education of a harmoniously developed generation and the ability to consistently apply them in their future careers [1].

In modern society, the level of development of a country is determined not only by its technical condition, but also by the professional competence of specialists trained in higher education institutions. Because the education system has a place in the world, building a prestigious society, ensuring the democratic development of our country and the formation of civil society, its democratization and liberalization, raising the level of political, legal, spiritual, moral, social consciousness and worldview of citizens. is the foundation of the formation. That is why today one of the directions in the education system - the innovative activity of educational institutions - is identified as a key factor. Every prospective specialist should understand the need to reform the education system and its importance in practice in the integration of educational institutions in the innovation process, as well as to see themselves in the innovative field where there is an opportunity to create and, most importantly, to learn.

There are huge pedagogical and psychological opportunities in the formation and development of creative qualities of the individual, in the realization of which the correct organization of theoretical research and practical activities is crucial. In this regard, the organization of professional creativity of future teachers has a special place due to its versatility and complex structure [2].

It is known from pedagogical observations that many vocational education teachers, young professionals who have just started working in colleges, face certain difficulties in organizing the creative activities of students. In this sense, one of the most pressing issues is the training of future teachers of vocational education to lead the creative activities of students in professional colleges.

Educating future professionals in the spirit of love for their chosen profession and work, enriching their spirituality and professional culture in many respects depends on the qualities of professional creativity formed in the teacher. Guiding any creativity, especially professional-oriented creativity, requires excellent professional knowledge and skills from the teacher.

In order to prepare the pedagogical staff trained in the areas of vocational education to lead students in professional creative activities, first of all, it is necessary to define its strategy. This strategic system includes:

- Always draw students' attention to the universality of the method used to solve the problem. As a result, students become accustomed to looking for new laws and solutions by applying the method used in the classroom to a particular situation;

- Teaching students creative methods is not seen as a goal of the lesson, but as a new way, an opportunity to more effectively solve the task set in the lesson. Tasks aimed at finding a solution to the problem involve analyzing the structure of the system under study and the processes within it. Therefore, the correct definition of the expected goal of solving the problem and the tasks in its implementation will benefit more than the efforts to solve the problem immediately;

- New ideas, which students can draw their own conclusions, are the main "product" of creative lessons. However, finding a new solution to the problem alone should not be the last stage of creative activity. The fact that students learn to "finish" their ideas, that is, to acquire certain skills to try, justify and implement a new solution, creates the necessary basis for raising creativity from the level of "imagination" to the practical stage. Another important aspect of this review is that it prepares the ground for ensuring a

high level of activity in the future professional activities of students and, ultimately, for educating future scientists who will conduct in-depth research in various fields of science;

- An important aspect of creativity is the collection, analysis and interpretation of information, without which any method of creativity loses its relevance. In the formation of students' initial skills in working with information, it is possible to use a wide range of methods to engage them in the collection, sorting and systematization of Internet materials, photographs, scientific and popular articles, etc.;

- A very important issue in the scope of classes in educational institutions, which goes beyond lessons and extracurricular activities - is the development of creative qualities of the individual. Usually when talking about great scientists and inventors, students try to avoid trying to say, "Only great scientists have achieved such great things, and we are ordinary people." One of the important ways to overcome this notion is to acquaint students with the biographies of famous artists with different lifestyles, which will need to accurately describe all aspects of the life of the person in question. At the heart of this method is the need to inculcate in students the idea that the highest achievements in science can be achieved by anyone who aspires to it [3, 4, 5, 6].

In the teaching of such disciplines as vocational education methodology, descriptive geometry and engineering graphics, interchangeability standardization and technical measurements, technology of construction materials, technical creativity and design, hydraulics, machine parts, prospects of technical development, design of technological equipment extensive use of related learning assignments [7].

Prospective vocational education teachers include visual aids, equipment and devices for departmental training laboratories or training workshops, dynamometer wrenches, a device for dynamic balancing of rotating masses, a device for studying the kinematic properties of hinged mechanisms, cutting, bending and torsion angles of two support and cantilever beams detection device; a device for determining the virginity of cylindrical springs, can design and prepare experimental samples of devices for determining the transition to laminar flow in pipes and for determining the characteristics of a gear pump. Students can voluntarily carry out circle work on the basis of training workshops of professional colleges operating in cooperation with the university. In doing so, they can perform creative learning tasks, mainly related to the preparation of small-scale constructions and models of modern technical equipment.

In this process, the process of creating models and technical devices can be carried out in the following stages: study of the training task; selection of the type of model and preparation of the terms of reference; selection of the work to be performed by the constructed object, the solution to be developed and the means of its solution; to get acquainted with the design and solutions close to the solution on the basis of photos, drawings or other documents; drawing up a scheme for the development of the design; drawing up a design scheme and determining the principle of its operation, substantiation of the engine type; determine the number of parts and their functions; perform elementary calculations of details and components, choose methods of their connection; identify the material of parts and assemblies required for preparation; development of technical documentation and preparation of the object; making amendments to the technical documentation prepared on the basis of the study of the prepared object; Carrying out the final equipment and finishing works, calculation of the cost of manufacturing the product, development of proposals to improve the quality of the product and reduce costs.

In preparing future teachers of vocational education to lead students in professional creative activities, it is important to conduct pedagogical research on the methodology of vocational education and the preparation of qualifying dissertations based on its results [8, 9].

In order to prepare future teachers of vocational education to lead the professional creativity of students in professional colleges, it is necessary to develop in them the skills to combine knowledge of pedagogy and methodology with the areas of vocational training. In this process, it is also necessary to effectively use the opportunities to acquaint students with the methods of formation of inventive, design skills in students.

In short, the thorough mastery of the methods of organizing professional creativity among future teaching staff, along with the methods of vocational education, provides the creation of the necessary methodological framework to ensure the quality of vocational education.

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ЗАВИСИМОСТЕЙ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КАЧЕСТВА ТРИКОТАЖНОГО ПОЛОТНА ОТ ДОЛЕВОГО СОДЕРЖАНИЯ ПОЛИЭФИРНЫХ ВОЛОКОН

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АННОТАЦИЯ: В статье приведены результаты сравнительной характеристики физико-механических свойств трикотажных полотен различного волокнистого состава и определена зависимость удельной разрывной нагрузки по длине от содержания в смеси полиэфирных волокон. Представлены результаты испытаний разрывной нагрузки, растяжимость по ширине, воздухопроницаемость, гигроскопичность, усадка.

Для определения влияние волокнистого состава на свойства прессового трикотажа при помощи современных приборов были определены следующие физико-механические и структурные показатели, представленные в таблице 1.

	Наименование показателей	Образ ец1	Образ ец 2	Образ ец3
	Волокнистый состав, %	100 х/б	60 х/б 40 ПЭ	80 х/б 20 ПЭ
	Переплетение	пресс овое	пресс овое	Пресс овое
	Поверхностное плотность гр/м ²	155,7	136,0	147,6
	Разрывная нагрузка по длине, по ширине, N	228,0	241,0	231,0
		108,6	186,0	171,0
5	Относительная разрывная нагрузка по длине,% по ширине	29,29	35,44	31,30
		13,94	27,35	23,17
	Растяжимость по ширине, св 6 N	29,0	38,0	34,0
	Воздухопроницаемость, см ³ /см ² сек	186,8	253,1	211,9

	Гигроскопичность, %	10,6	9,3	5,1
0	Усадка, %			
	По длине	-5,0	-2,5	-4,5
	По ширине	-4,5	-3,0	-3,5
1	Истирание	18000	21000	20000
2	Петельный шаг, мм	0,89	0,88	0,83
3	Высота петли, мм	0,77	0,77	0,77
4	Плотность по горизонтали	56	57	60
5	Плотность по вертикали	65	65	65
6	Длина петли	3,10	3,49	3,15

Изучая данные таблицы 1 видно, что зависимость между удельной разрывной нагрузкой по длине, растяжимость по ширине при 6Н, (Y_1 , Y_2 ,) от содержания в трикотажном полотне полиэфирных волокон (X) линейная вида:

$$Y = ax + b$$

Коэффициенты a и b определяем по методу наименьших квадратов по формулам:

$$a = \frac{n \cdot \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \cdot \sum y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$b = \frac{\sum y_i \cdot \sum x_i^2 - \sum x_i \cdot \sum x_i y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

Для величин, входящих в эти формулы составляем таблицы 2 и 3.

Таблица 2

Зависимость удельной разрывной нагрузки по длине Y_1 от содержания в смеси полиэфирных волокон

Содержание ПЭ, X, %	Удельная разрывная нагрузка, Y_i	x^2	xy_1
0	29,29	0	0
20	31,30	400	626,0
40	35,44	1600	1417,6
$\sum x = 60$	$\sum y_i = 96,03$	$\sum x^2 = 2000$	$\sum xy_1 = 2043,6$

$$a = \frac{3 \cdot 2043,6 - 60 \cdot 96,03}{3 \cdot 2000 - 60 \cdot 60} = \frac{369}{2400} = 0,154, \quad (3)$$

$$b = \frac{96,03 \cdot 2000 - 60 \cdot 2043,6}{3 \cdot 2000 - 60 \cdot 60} = \frac{69,444}{24000} = 28,94 \quad (4)$$

Уравнение принимает вид $Y_1 = 0,154x + 28,94$, (5)

Из уравнения 5 видно, что при увеличении содержания полиэфирных волокон в смеси на каждые 10% удельная разрывная нагрузка прессового трикотажного полотна увеличивается на 1,54 сН/текс.

Таблица 3

Зависимость растяжимости по ширине Y_2 от процентного содержания полиэфирных полотен (X)

Содержание отхода X, %	Растяжимость по ширине при 6Н, %	x^2	xy_1
0	29,0	0	0
20	34,0	400	680
40	38,0	1600	1520
$\sum x = 60$	$\sum y_i = 101$	$\sum x^2 = 2000$	$\sum xy_1 = 2200$

$$a = \frac{3 \cdot 2200 - 60 \cdot 101}{3 \cdot 2000 - 60 \cdot 60} = \frac{540}{2400} = 0,225, \quad (6)$$

$$b = \frac{101 \cdot 2000 - 60 \cdot 2200}{3 \cdot 2000 - 60 \cdot 60} = \frac{70000}{2400} = 29,17, \quad (7)$$

Уравнение принимает вид

$$Y_2 = 0,225x + 29,17, \quad (8)$$

Из уравнения 8 видно, что с увеличением содержания полиэфирных волокон каждые 10% растяжимость по ширине увеличивается на 2,25% (абс)

Составлены эмпирические формулы зависимостей показателей качества трикотажного полотна от долевого содержания волокон: при увеличении содержания полиэфирных волокон в смеси на каждые 10% удельная разрывная нагрузка прессового трикотажного полотна увеличивается на 1,54 сН/текс, с увеличением содержания полиэфирных волокон каждые 10% растяжимость по ширине увеличивается на 2,25% (абс).

Полученные эмпирические формулы позволяют прогнозировать качество пряжи и обрывность на прядильных машинах при изменении долевого содержания компонентов.

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ВЛИЯНИЕ ВОЛОКНИСТОГО СОСТАВА ПРЕССОВОГО ТРИКОТАЖНОГО ПОЛОТНА НА ДЕФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ СВОЙСТВА

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Аннотация

В статье приведены результаты влияния волокнистого состава на деформационные свойства трикотажных полотен прессового переплетения. По приведённым результатам испытаний построены графики изменения размеров образцов трикотажных полотен при нагрузке и разгрузке образцов в течение 60 минут.

Прессовое переплетение (или «лакоста») характеризуется наличием рельефных и ажурных узоров различной формы, образующихся благодаря особенностям вязания и придающих изделию красивый внешний вид, например «соты». Полотнам прессового переплетения свойственны малая растяжимость и значительная плотность. Переплетение используется для изготовления верхних, мужских джемперов, поло, женских футболок. На рисунке 1 приведено графическое изображение трикотажных полотен прессового переплетения.

Фанг

Полуфанг

Рис.1 Прессовое переплетение

Рисунчатый (прессовый) комплекс состоит из прессовой петли и петель, величина строения которых отличается от фоновой структуры. Известно, что прессовая петля влияет на рядом расположенные петли, за счет чего происходит изменение линейных размеров трикотажа.

Проявление составных частей деформации растяжения трикотажа по сравнению с тканями имеет некоторые особенности,

определяемые петельным строением трикотажа. Прессовые петли отличаются от обычных большей высотой и имеют наброски (незамкнутые петли). Если в полотне все петли прессовые, то это переплетение называют фангом; если петельные столбики прессовых петель чередуются с петельными столбиками глади, то это переплетение называется полуфанг. Так, незначительное увеличение статической нагрузки при кратковременном ее действии приводит к резкому увеличению полного удлинения с преимущественным развитием упругой деформации. Со временем действия статической нагрузки изменяется соотношение частей полной деформации растяжения трикотажа: обратимая часть деформации уменьшается, необратимая часть растет. При значительном увеличении статической нагрузки увеличивается остаточная часть полной деформации трикотажа. Таким образом, чем меньше нагрузка, действующая на материал, и время ее действия, тем больше доля упругой компоненты. Поэтому одежда, материал которой при носке испытывает кратковременное действие незначительной нагрузки, лучше сохраняет форму и размеры. Поэтому большой интерес представляет изучение характеристик механических свойств, получаемых при испытании по циклу «нагрузка-разгрузка-отдых», а именно полной деформации и ее составных частей. В трикотаже внешние связи определяются силами трения и сцепления, возникающими между нитями петель. При приложении силы происходит изменение структуры трикотажа, изменяются форма и размеры петель, отдельные участки нити в петлях распрямляются, другие изгибаются

Для выбора оптимального варианта прессового трикотажного полотна, по стандартной методике были определены релаксационные характеристики при растяжении для расчёта составных частей деформации у трех вариантов трикотажных полотен различного волокнистого состава 100 х/б, 60 х/б+ 40 ПЭ, 80 х/б+20 ПЭ.

При этом, используются релаксометры типа «стойки» для испытаний при постоянной нагрузке. При этом, одноцикловые характеристики полотен определяют при следующих параметрах: зажимная длина для образцов составляет – 100 мм, ширина пробных полосок 50 мм, постоянная нагрузка от разрывной 5%. Результаты испытаний деформационных характеристик приведены в таблицах 1 и 2.

Изменение размеров трикотажного полотна во времени при определении составных частей деформации

Таблица 1

1-вариант		2-вариант		3-вариант	
По длине	По ширине	По длине	По ширине	По длине	По ширине
10	10	10	10	10	10
13,3	13,7	14,7	14,2	15	14,3
13,7	14,2	15,0	14,4	15,3	14,5
13,9	14,4	15,3	14,5	15,6	14,6
14,2	14,6	15,7	14,7	15,8	14,8
14,3	14,8	15,9	14,9	15,9	14,9
14,5	15	16	15	16	15
11,0	11,7	13,0	11,3	12,3	11,8
10,9	11,0	12,5	11,0	12,1	11,7
10,7	10,8	12,0	10,7	11,7	11,6
10,6	10,7	11,5	10,5	11,0	11,6
10,5	10,6	11,3	10,4	10,8	11,5
10,4	10,5	11,0	10,3	10,7	11,5

Составные части деформации прессового трикотажа

Таблица 2

Варианты	Волокнистый состав	Остаточная деформация		Обратимая деформация	
		По длине	По ширине	По длине	По ширине
I	100 х/б	9	10	91	90
II	60 х/б+ 40 ПЭ	17	6	83	94
III	80 х/б+20 ПЭ	12	30	88	70

Очевидно, что удлинение трикотажа, особенно, в первый период растяжения, происходит, главным образом, из-за изменений в его макроструктуре: увеличивается степень ориентации элементарных звеньев за счет ликвидации телескопического захода и сближении остовов петель в направлении, нормальном силовому полю.

Из приведённых результатов в таблице и по графикам видно, что образец 1 имеет большую по значению обратимую деформацию по длине и по ширине, соответственно 91% и 90%, что на 8% по длине больше и на 4% по ширине меньше чем у образца 2, на 3% по длине и на 20% по ширине больше чем у образца 3. Это можно объяснить тем, что образец 3 имеет рисунчатый эффект, где петельные столбики прессовых петель чередуются с петельными столбиками глади, то это переплетение называется полуфанг, а у образца 1 в полотне все петли

прессовые, то это переплетение называют фангом. При этом, поверхностная плотность образца 1 больше чем у других образцов за счёт большего индекса петли равную 2, то есть, на петле может быть от одной до нескольких набросков, от их количества зависит индекс прессовой петли. Индекс прессовой петли равен числу ее набросков.

Таким образом, при изучение деформационных свойств определили, что образец 1 имеет большую по значению обратимую деформацию по длине и по ширине, соответственно 91% и 90%, что на 8% по длине больше и на 4% по ширине меньше чем у образца 2, на 3% по длине и на 20% по ширине больше чем у образца 3.

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Влияние гормона роста на обменные процессы в разных тканях.

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АННОТАЦИЯ Представлены результаты исследований роли гормона роста в метаболизме, а также получение короткого курса рГР у взрослых-спортсмены любители и изменения метаболических, функциональных и психологических результатов. Ключевые слова: Гормон роста (GH), жировой ткань, рекомбинантный гормон роста, метаболизм, соматотрофы, соматотропина.

Актуальность темы исследования.

Соматотропный гормон – это смесь разнообразных изоформ, вариантов, фрагментов и связывающих протеинов. Самая распространенная изоформа– именно ее –представляет собой последовательность из 191 аминокислоты и весит 22 кда (если более точно,то 22124 дальтона). На основе этого гормона создано множество синтетических препаратов с лучшей биодоступностью и большим анаболическим эффектом. Как известно, гормон роста (ГР) был последним из классических гормонов, который начали использовать с целью заместительной гормональной терапии у взрослых. У детей история медикаментозной коррекции низкорослости насчитывает около тридцати лет, у взрослых лечение биосинтетическими препаратами ГР впервые было применено около 15 лет назад. В течение многих лет для терапии использовали ГР, полученный из экстрактов гипофиза, но в 1985 г., когда было описано четыре случая болезни Крейтцфельда—Якоба у реципиентов гипофизарного ГР, использование последнего было запрещено. Это послужило отправной точкой для начала работ по производству биосинтетических ГР [2].

Соматропин по технологии (Protein Secretion Technology), производится рГР, являющийся полным аналогом– самой распространенной изоформы, состоящей из 191 аминокислоты. Гормон роста необходим для роста тела, но он также модулирует метаболические пути, а также нервную, репродуктивную, иммунную, сердечно-сосудистую и легочную функции. Многочисленные положительные эффекты гормона роста привели к расширению его терапевтического использования как у детей, так и у взрослых. Есть несколько официально одобренных применений гормона роста человека и еще много предложенных применений, которые являются результатом огромного количества клинических исследований по

терапии ГР. Злоупотребление гормоном роста включает неправильное или чрезмерное использование. За последнее десятилетие ГР стал одним из наиболее часто употребляемых наркотиков в спорте из-за того, что его прием в настоящее время не поддается обнаружению. Огромные дозы, которые вводятся инъекционно, и частое одновременное злоупотребление другими веществами, такими как другие анаболические стероиды (тестостерон), приводят к частым побочным эффектам. В спорте в качестве допингового средства он впервые был испробован лишь в 1982 году а в 1989 году его официально назвали допингом. Изначально в спорте гормон роста использовался для лечения травм. Что и неудивительно, так как занятия спортом можно считать едва ли не основным источником всевозможных повреждений. Но только этим использование столь замечательного препарата ограничиться не могло.

Гормоны в значительной степени отвечают за интегрированную связь нескольких физиологических систем, отвечающих за модуляцию клеточного роста и развития. Хотя специфическое влияние гормонов следует рассматривать в контексте всей эндокринной системы и ее связи с другими физиологическими системами, три ключевых гормона считаются «анаболическими гигантами» в клеточном росте и восстановлении: тестостерон, гормон роста и инсулиноподобный фактора роста (ИФР-1).

Как и многие гормоны, ГР синтезируется в определенном импульсном режиме, пики секреции приходятся на 22.00 и 4.00 часа.

Сильное снижение ночного производства гормона роста даже не после 50 лет, а гораздо раньше –после 25-30 лет. Если у 25-летнего человека гипофиз производит ночью в среднем 350 мкг соматотропина (больше 1 МЕ), то у 35-летнего –не более 170-200 мкг (примерно 0,5-0,6 МЕ). А это говорит о том, что начинать стимулировать хотя бы ночное производство гормона роста с помощью пептидных стимуляторов стоит в относительно молодом возрасте. Гормоны с анаболическими свойствами, такие как гормон роста , инсулиноподобный фактор роста-1 и инсулин, обычно злоупотребляют профессиональными спортсменами и спортсменами-любителями для улучшения физических возможностей. Подобные препараты, повышающие работоспособность, также широко используются спортсменами-любителями для улучшения эстетики тела. Восприятие увеличения мышечной массы из-за супрафизиологических гормональных добавок или допинга широко распространено среди пользователей.

•**Цель работы:** Оценить спектр метаболических эффектов у взрослых, получающих короткий курс рекомбинантного гормон роста

Задачи исследования:

Оценить гормональные показатели у взрослых (спортсмены-любители) при проведении анаболическую терапии препаратами рГР

Оценить клинико-биохимические показатели у взрослых (спортсмены-любители) при проведении анаболическую терапии препаратами рГР

Оценить качество жизни у взрослых (спортсмены-любители) проходивших анаболическую терапию препаратом рГР с контрольной группой

Материалы и методы исследования.

В это исследование были включены мужчины в возрасте от 25 до 40 лет, разделенные на 2 гр: 1- группа (n = 30) спортсмены-любители), здоровых спортсменов-любителей мужского пола, принимающих гормон роста в комбинации ААС ;2-группа никогда не принимавшие в качестве контрольной группы (n = 30) добровольно приняли участие в исследовании.

Ограничения: Протоколы гормона роста в исследованиях могут не отражать реальные дозы и режимы.

Клинические: анамнез, антропометрия: рост, вес, ИМТ, Соотношения талии к бедрам, ОТ,ОБ, общий клинический осмотр.

Лабораторные анализы

Лабораторные анализы: ОАК, глюкоза натощак, инсулин, триглицерид, СТГ, ИФР-1, НВА1с, Холестерин, ТТГ,свТ4, обТЗ, тестостерон, МРТ гипофиза.

Научная новизна исследования

Полученные результаты позволят оценить влияние гормон роста в комбинации с др. препаратами на метаболические изменение, биохимические и гормональные изменение физически активных добровольцев. Необходимы более крупные многоцентровые хорошо спланированные исследования для лучшего описания и количественной оценки влияние на организм рГР и ААС.

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**БОЛАЛАРДА ЎТКИР БИТИШМАЛИ ИЧАК ТУТИЛИШНИ
ДАВОЛАШ ВА ДИАГНОСТИКАСИДА ЭНДОВИДЕОЛАПАРОСКОПИК
ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ АХАМИЯТИ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада марказда 2012-2021 йиллар давомида ўткир битишмали ичак тутилиши билан 57 нафар беморларда эндовидеолапароскопик хирургик амалиётлар таҳлиллари келтирилган. Мурожаат қилган барча беморларда марказда қабул қилинган клиник даволаш-диагностик алгоритм бўйича олиб борилди. Операциядан олдинги диагностика мақсадида клиник, лаборатор, рентгенологик, ва УТТ текширув усулларида иборат бўлди. Бу беморларда ҳам консерватив даво муолажалари самара бермагандан сўнг 5-16 соат оралиғида хирургик амалиётлар амалга оширилди. Шулардан 9 нафарида эндовидеолапароскопик хирургик амалиёти бажарилди. Хулоса қилиб шуни айтиш мумкин-ки болаларда ўткир битишмали ичак тутилишида видеолапароскопик адгезиолизис ўтказилиши операция шикастини камайтиради, қайта битишма ҳосил бўлиши хавфини 3,3 баробар пасайтиради, асоратларнинг камайишига эришилади.

Калит сўзлар: Битишмали касаллик, ўткир битишмали ичак тутилиши, профилактика, болалар, видеолапароскопик адгезиолизис.

Муаммони долзарблиги: Ҳозирги замонавий тиббиётнинг долзарб муаммоларидан бири қорин бўшлиғи битишма касаллиги ҳисобланади.

Қорин бўшлиғида битишмалар пайдо бўлиши, қорин бўшлиғи органларини йирингли яллиғланиш касалликлари, травмалари, қорин бўшлиғида ўтказилган хирургик операциялардан сўнг ҳосил бўлиши билан характерланади.

Тадқиқотимиз мақсади: Болаларда ўткир битишмали ичак тутилиши даволаш ва диагностикасида эндовидеолапароскопик технологияни қўллаш самарадорлиги, қулайликларини баҳолашдан иборат.

Материал ва текшириш усуллари: Республика Болалар кам инвазив ва эндовизуал илмий-амалий марказида 2012-2021 йиллар давомида ўткир битишмали ичак тутилиши билан эндовидеолапароскопик хирургик амалиётлар 57 нафар болаларда бажарилди. Улардан ўғил болалар-24нафар, қиз болалар бўлса 33 нафар бўлиб, ўртача ёшлари 5 ёшдан 17 ёшгача ташкил этиб, операция бўлган беморларни 37,8% ни ташкил этади. 57 нафар бемор болалардан эрта битишмали ичак тутилиши гумони билан 10 нафари мурожаат қилган бўлиб, касаллик бошланиш муддати 4 соатдан 5 суткача бўлиб, ўртача 16,1+4,3 соатни ташкил этади. Мурожаат қилган барча беморларда марказда қабул қилинган клиник даволаш-диагностик алгоритм бўйича олиб борилди. Операциядан олдинги диагностика мақсадида клиник, лабаратор, рентгенологик, ва УТТ текширув усулларида иборат бўлди. Неинвазив диагностика босқичида битишмали ичак тутилишини икки асосий формаларини ажратдик: 1) Странгуляцион осбструктив натижасида ичак пассажи бузилиши ва органда қон айланиши бузилиш белгиларини пайдо бўлиши 32 та беморда кузатилди. Бу беморлар стационарга мурожаат қилгандан сўнг 2-4 соат оралиғида операция муолажаси бажарилди. 2) Ўткир битишмали ичак тутилишини оддий формаси бўлиб, ичак пассажи бузилиши кузатилиб, органларда қон айланиши бузилишини клиник белгилари намоён бўлмаган беморлар 25тани ташкил этди. Бу беморларда ҳам консерватив даво муолажалари самара бермагандан сўнг 5-16 соат оралиғида хирургик амалиётлар амалга оширилди. Шулардан 9 тасида эндовизуал лапароскопик хирургик амалиёти бажарилди. Эндовизуал лапароскопик хирургик амалиётига ўткир битишмали ичак тутилишида ичак некрози белгилари аниқланса, перитонит, организмда чуқур сув-электролитлари ва кислота-ишқор

мувозанатида ўзгаришлар кетганда қарши кўрсатма бўлиб ҳисобланди:

Натижалар: Қорин бўшлиғига Вереш нинасини киритишда қорин деворидаги операциядан кейинги чандиқ атрофи УТТ текшируви ўтказилганидан сўнг стандарт бўлмаган жойиларидан, бунда ичак қовузлоқларини шикастлаб қўймаслик мақсадида, қорин бўшлиғи ички деворида битишмалар йўқ жойидан киритилишга ҳаракат қилинди. Қорин бўшлиғи видеолапароскопик ревизия қилинган 29(43,2%) беморларни ичак некрози билан-(5), ичак ҳаётлиги гумони билан-(6), қорин бўшлиғида кўпламчи битишмали конгломерати билан-(9), тарқалган битишмали жараёнлар билан-(7), ичаклар парези ҳисобига ингичка ичак қовузлоқларини кенгайиши билан-(2) беморларда битишмали ичак тугилишини видеолапароскопик адгезиолизис ўтказишга қарши кўрсатма бўлиб ҳисобланди. 2(1,2%) та беморда ўткир битишмали касаллиги ташхиси тасдиқланмади. Ўткир битишмали ичак тугилиши билан 38(55,6%) беморларни 32(47,3%) тасида битишмали ичак тугилишини видеолапароскопик усулда бартараф этишга эришилди. Бу беморларда операция маҳали ва операция кейинги даврларда эрта ва кечки асоратлар кузатилмади.

Хулоса: Болаларда ўткир битишмали ичак тугилишида видеолапароскопик адгезиолизис ўтказилиши операция шикастини камайтиради, қайта битишма ҳосил бўлиши хавфини 3,3 баробар пасайтиради, асоратларнинг камайиши, операция амалиётига кетадиган вақт, беморнинг физик активлигининг тикланиши, беморнинг ҳаёт сифатини яхшилайти ва яхши косметик самара қолдиради.

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ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 1950-1970 ЙИЛЛАРДА СОАВХОЗЛАРДА УЙ-ЖОЙ МУАММОЛАРИ.

ТДАУ “Гуманитар фанлар” кафедраси
катта ўқитувчиси, Ҳ.О.Хушвақтов.

Аннотаци: Мақолада 1950-1970 йилларда Ўзбекистонда янги ўзлаштирилган худудларда ташкил этилган совхозларда аҳолининг уй-жой муаммолари акс эттирилган.

Ўзбекистонда мустақилликни қўлга киритилишининг илк кунлариданоқ, қишлоқларда яшовчи аҳолининг ижтимоий - иқтисодий аҳолини яхшилаш ва уларга муносиб яшаш шароитларини яратиб бериш давлатимиз сиёсатининг устивор йўналишига айланди ва улкан ишлар амалга оширилди. Бу ишларнинг давоми сифатида, ҳукуратимиз томонидан 2009 – йилни “Қишлоқ тараққиёти ва фаровонлиги йили” деб эълон қилишни таклиф этилиши, қишлоқ аҳолисининг ижтимоий – иқтисодий ва маънавий тараққиётини таъминлашда яна бир муҳим қадам бўлди. Қишлоқ аҳолисининг ижтимоий –иқтисодий, сиёсий ва маданий турмуш даражасини юксалтиришга қаратилган ушбу давлат дастурида қишлоқлардаги ишлаб чиқариш инфратузилмасини ривожлантириш, табиий ресурсларидан, шу жумладан, сув ресурсларидан оқилона фойдаланиш, қишлоқ ҳаёти сифатини янада яхшилаш, минтақаларнинг иқлими, демографик ҳолати ва бошқа шарт – шароитларни ҳисобга олган ҳолда қишлоқларда намунавий лойиҳалар асосида уй – жойларнинг барпо этилиши қабтий белгилаб қўйилди. Президентимиз, Ш. Мирзиёев таъкидлаганидек, - “Бизнинг энг жиддий камчиликларимиздан бири-замонавий талабларга жавоб берадиган лойиҳа институтларининг йўқлигидир. Уларнинг моддий-техник базаси ўтган асрнинг 80 – йиллари даражасида қолиб кетган”¹ деб таъкидлайди. Маълумки, совет ҳукмронлиги йилларида маъмурий буйруқбозлик тизими доирасида иқтисодиётнинг мафкура измига тўла бўйсундирилиши шароитида фақат марказ манфаатлари йўлида амалга оширилган ислоҳотлар республика аҳолисининг ижтимоий-иқтисодий ҳаётига самарали таъсир кўрсатмади. “Аксинча,-деб таъкидлайди Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Биринчи Президент И.Каримов, - сўнги йиллар мобайнида сохта обрў орттириш мақсадида қабул қилинган ва мавжуд имкониятларни ҳисобга олмаган

¹ Мирзиёев Ш. “Танқидий таҳлил, қатъий тартиб-интизом ва шахсий жавобгарлик-ҳар бир раҳбар фаолиятининг кундалик қондаси бўлиши керак”. Тошкент. “Ўзбекистон”, 2017 й.24 Б.

ижтимоий, озиқ-овқат, аграр, энергетика, экология ва бошқа соҳалардаги кўпгина дастурлар иқтисодий қарама-қаршиликларни чуқурлаштириб юборди. Натижада иқтисодиётни батамом издан чиқариб, моддий ва молиявий маблағлар тақчиллигининг даҳшатли тарзда ўсишига олиб келди”². Марказий ҳокимият Иттифоқ меҳнат тақсимотида, ягона халқ хўжалиги комплексида Ўзбекистоннинг асосий ўрни пахтачиликдан иборат эканлиги қатъий белгилаб қўйилди. Шу мақсадда, 1946 – йил 2 – февралдаги “Ўзбекистон ССР да пахтачиликни ривожлантириш чора тадбирлари ҳақидаги” қароридан кейин, янги ўзлаштирилган ерларга, шу жумладан Мирзачўлга аҳолини кўчириш тадбирлари янада кучайтирилди³. Натижада, пахта етиштиришни кўпайтиришга астойдил киришиб, аҳоли зич яшайдиган вилоят ва туманлардан янги ўзлаштирилаётган ерларга аҳолини кўчиришга эътиборини янада кучайтирди. “Янги ўзлаштирилган ерларга республикамизнинг асосан суғорилмайдиган деҳқончилик районларидан жумладан, Мирзачўлга 40 минг колхозчи хўжалиги кўчириб келтирилсин”⁴, деб қатъий белгилаб қўйилди ва доимий назорат қилиб турди. Уни бажармаслик “жиноий иш” деб баҳоланди. Мирзачўлга 1950 йилгача кўпроқ, Ғаллаорол, Фориш, Зомин, Ховос ва қўшни хўжаликлардан кейинчалик Фарғона, Тошкент, Самарқанд вилоятларидан аҳоли кўчириб келтирилган. Бироқ, чўлга кўчириб келтирилган аҳолининг аҳволи қониқарли ҳолда бўлмаган, уларга шароит-шароитлар яратилмаган, аниқроғи ташкил қилинмаган. Масалан, “Самарқанд вилояти Пойариқ туманидан Мирзачўлга кўчирилганлар уч ойлаб озиқ – овқат билан таъминланмай, бу ҳолатда очликкача етиб борганлар. Саноат моллари айниқса, ёғ ва совун норма маҳсулотлари берилмаган. Таъминотдаги суринкали узилишлар қочоқликнинг авж олишига сабаб бўлган”⁵. Ҳукумат томонидан амалга оширилган тадбирлар чўлга кўчиб борганларнинг ҳошиш – иродасига қарши борар, улар орасида ижтимоий ҳолатнинг кескинлашувига, уларнинг норозилигига сабаб бўлди. “Кўчириб келтирилган аҳоли жойлаштирилган ерлардаги яшаш шароитининг талаб даражасида ташкил қилинмаганлиги сабабли натижада, 3467 оила, ёки кўчиб келган аҳолининг 19,2 фоизи қайтиб кетган”⁶ Тўғри, кўчиб келган аҳолини уй-жой билан таъминлашда имтиёзлар ҳам

² Каримов И.А. Ўзбекистон: миллий истиқлол, иқтисод, сиёсат, мафкура.-Т.:Ўзбекистон, 1996. 280-бет.

³ ЎзРМА.314 – фонд,1 – рўйхат,415 – йиғма жилд, 10 – варақ.

⁴ ЎзРМА.314 – фонд,1 – рўйхат,415 – йиғма жилд, 16 – варақ.

⁵ ЎзР МДА 95 – фонд.,2-рўй,2606-иш, 7-8 варақ

⁶ ЎзМДА 837 – фонд,33 – рйхат,5753 – йиғма жилд,49– варақ.

берилган. Масалан, “Кўчувчилар енгилликларни олишга ҳаққли эканликларини тасдиқлайдиган ҳужжат кўчириш оргонлари томонидан берилган кўчувчининг билети бўлади”⁷. Бундай имтиёзлардан кўчаётган ва кўчиб борган ҳамма аҳоли ҳам фойдалана олмаган. Аниқроғи, қандай фойдаланишнинг тартиб қодаларини ҳаммаси ҳам тушунмаган. Бундай енгилликлардан фойдаланишга аниқроғи ҳуқуқи бўлмаган. Имтиёзлар, фақат партия кўрсатмаларида ва матбуот материалларида аҳолини янги ерларга кўпроқ жалб қилишнинг бир кўриниши эди, ҳалос. Шунини алоҳида таъкидлаш керакки, никоҳ масаласига ҳам алоҳида эътибор қаратиш керак бўлади. Аҳолини кўчириш сиёсати янги ўзлаштирилган ҳудудлардаги янги совхозларда яшаётган аҳолининг миллий таркибига ҳам ўз таъсирини ўтказди. Янги ташкил топган совхозларда бир неча миллат вакиллари билан бир жойга тўпланиши, бирга ишлаши ва яшаши натижасида миллатларaro оилалар вужудга келди. “Аҳолининг кўчирилишида темир йўл бўйлаб кетиши кўпинча стихияли тарзда амалга оширилган. Кўчирилаётган аҳоли олдиндан огоҳлантирилмаган ва очиқ тайёргарлик кўрилмаган. Айрим ҳолларда кўчирилувчилар поезд станцияларида бир неча кунлаб очиқ жойда ва совуқда қолиб кетганлар”⁸. Шунини таъкидлаш керакки, маҳаллий иқлим шароитига мос келмайдиган, аҳоли менталитетини ҳисобга олмаган ҳолда шошма-шошарлик билан қурилган темир-бетонли уй – жойлар кўчирилган аҳолининг моддий ва маънавий эҳтиёжларини қондира олмади. Натижада, Мирзачўлга кўчирилган аҳолининг кўпчилиги орқага қайтиб кетди. Бу эса кадрлар қўнимсизлигига ва бошқа соҳаларга таъсир кўрсатди. Хулоса ўринда шунини айтиш керакки, Мирзачўлдаги қурилган уй-жойларни ҳозирги кунда қишлоқларда барча қулайликларга эга бўлган намунавий лойиҳалар асосида уй-жойлар қурилиши билан таққослаш асосида ўрганилаётган муаммонинг келиб чиқиш сабабларини англашимизга катта ёрдам беради. Бундан кўриш мумкинки кўчирилувчиларни жўнатишлар ва кутиб олишлар ташкил қилинмаган. Бошпана муаммоси ҳал этилмаган. Кўчирилганларнинг катта қисми, капаларда, чодирларда ва ертўлаларда яшашга мажбур бўлган. Улар рўйхатга туриб уй-жой олгунича қатор йиллар ўтган. Аниқроғи уларнинг кўчиб келганлигини расмийлаштириш ҳужжатлари қатор йиллар ўтгандан кейин расмийлаштирилган. Бундан шунини

⁷ Кўчириш юзасидан бериладиган енгилликлар тўғрисида. Колхоз раислари ва ташкилотчи раҳбарлар учун қўлланма. Тошкент. 1954 й. Ўздав нашр. 41 Б.

⁸ ЎзР МДА 95 - фонд, 2-рўйхат, 2206-иш, 40-варақ.

англаш мумкинки, бундай имтиёزلардан фойдаланиш ҳуқуқи ҳам бўлмаган. Бундай жараёнлар кўчирилганларнинг қочишларига сабаб бўлган. Чуқур ўйланмасдан олиб борилган бу ҳаракат минглаб кишиларнинг тақдирида ўзгаришлар ясади, тuzатиш машаққатли бўлган излар қолдирди.

Texnologiya darslarida inglizcha krassvordlardan foydalanish

Bizga ma'lumki o'quvchilarga yangi bilimlar berishda darsning noan'anaviy usullaridan foydalanish juda yaxshi natija berishi bilan birgalikda o'quvchilarda darsga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini oshirish, yangi g'oyalar ustida ishlash, ko'nikma hosil qilish hamda ularni ijodkorlikga undaydi. Yangi va ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash, kompyuter savodxonligini oshirish, internet ma'lumotlaridan foydalanish esa o'quvchilarni ommaviy axborot vositalaridan o'zlari uchun kerakli ma'lumotlarni axtarib topishlari uchun eng qulay imkoniyatdir. Texnologiya fanini o'qitishda xorijiy tillardan foydalanish, ayniqsa ingliz tilidagi krossvordlardan foydalanish o'quvchilarda darslarga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini oshishiga hamda ularni erkin fikrlashlariga juda katta yordam beradi. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarni o'zlarini mustaqil fikrlashga hamda ijodiy izlanishlariga sabab bo'ladi. Biz bu ijodiy uslubni quyidagi usul bilan sinab ko'ramiz.

Avvalo o'quvchilarning ingliz tili savodxonligini tekshirib ko'ramiz, buning uchun ba'zi predmetlarni yoki mevalarni ko'rsatib uning o'zbekcha nomini so'raymiz, keyin esa inglizcha nomlanishini so'raymiz, shundan so'ng o'quvchilarni ikkita guruxga bo'lib olamiz. Xar bir guruxni nomlab gurux sardorini saylab olamiz, bunda o'quvchilardan o'zlarining guruxlaridagi ishonchli sinfdoshlarini sardor etib saylashlari kerakligini tushuntiramiz, chunki mashg'ulot yakunida sardorlar bellashuvini ham o'tkazish darsni qiziqarli bo'lishiga va o'quvchilarni faollikga hamda chaqqonlikga undaydi.

Krossvorddagi so'zlar faqat gorizontal xolatda yozilgan bo'lib, u yerda kalit so'zi “Technology” vertikal xolatda kelib chiqishi kerak.

Berilgan topshiriq krossvord.

1. Kiyimlarni birlashtiruvchi furnitura (tugma) -----> button
2. Gazlama kesuvchi qurol (qaychi) -----> shears
3. Rejalash quroli (bo'r) -----> chalk
4. Gazlamani tikish ish quroli (igna) -----> needle
5. O'quvchi korjomasi (fartuk) -----> apron
6. Barmoqni ximoyalovchi ish qurol (angishvona) -----> thimble
7. Kiyimlar uchun asosiy xom ashyo (gazlama) -----> manyfactory
8. Gazlamani birlashtiruvchi xom ashyo (ip) -----> string
9. Kiyimlarni bezagi (nozmunchoq) -----> drogonfey

Mashg'ulot davomida o'quvchilarga ko'rsatilgan predmetlarni qaysi gurux o'quvchilari birinchi bo'lib topsa ikkinchi gurux o'quvchilari uning nomini aytib izoxlab beradi, agar ikkinchi gurux o'quvchisi izoxlolmasa birinchi gurux o'quvchilarining o'zlari izoxlashlari va qo'shimcha balni qo'lga kiritishlari mumkin bo'ladi, bunda o'quvchilar qo'lga kiritgan ballar qanchalik ko'paysa ularning faolligi shunchalik oshib boradi. Yana shuni qo'shimcha aytish mumkinki, krassvorddagi berilgan topshiriqni o'quvchilar izoxlashganda uning rangini, nima uchun ishlatilishini, ya'ni vazifasini, uni qaerdan topish yoki sotib olish mumkinligi, umumiy yoki ayollar va erkaklar uchun aloxida turlari mavjud ekanligi to'g'risida ham o'z fikrlarini bayon qilishsa, berilgan topshiriqning javobi to'liq topilgan va izoxlangan bo'ladi. Mashg'ulotni xuddi shu usulda o'tib borilsa barcha o'quvchilarni tushunishlari oson bo'lishi bilan birga sinfdagi past o'zlashtiruvchi o'quvchilarning ham mashg'ulotni tushunishi oson bo'ladi.

Natija esa kutilgandek ijobiy bo'lishi bilan birga, keyingi mashg'ulotlarga o'quvchilarning o'zlarini ham yangi krassvord tuzib kelishlariga undaydi hamda izlanishlari samarasiga yarasha rag'bat olishlari uchun yangi imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lishadi.

Po'latov Rashidjon Farg'ona viloyati Beshariq tumani 11-maktab texnologiya fani o'qituvchisi.

Raximov Abduraufjon. FarDU I-bosqich magistranti. Beshariq tumani 38-maktab texnologiya fani o'qituvchisi

DOSTONLARDA ATOQLI OTLARNING QO'LLANILISHI

Axmedova So'najon

Urganch davlat universiteti Filologiya fakulteti

O'zbek tilshunosligi kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'zbek tili tarixida mavjud bo'lgan va ko'plab tarixiy yozma yodgorliklar hamda dostonlar tilida saqlanib turgan sanoqsiz atoqli otlarning qo'llanilishi xususida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: atoqli otlar, xalq dostonlari, joy nomlari, shaxs nomlari, tilshunoslik

Hozirgi davrda o'zbek tilidagi atoqli otlar tizimini zamonaviy tilshunoslik usullarida tadqiq qilish ayniqsa kuchaydi. Jumladan, joy nomlari, kishi nomlari va boshqa sohalar bo'yicha anchagina ilmiy ishlar qilindi. Binobarin, til sathimizda atoqli otlar juda kop, ularning barcha ko'rinishlarini to'plash va tarixiy taraqqiyotini o'rganish lozimdir.

Atoqli otlar bir marta nomlangan predmetlardan bittasini ajratish uchun qayta nomlangan ikkilamchi nomlardir. Atoqli otlar bilan ob'ektiv olamdagi narsalar o'rtasidagi aloqa so'zlovchi tomonidan o'rnatiladi. Agar ma'lum bir atoqli ot so'zlovchi tomonidan muayyan bir obyektga bog'lanmasa, u hech narsa bildirmaydi.

Ma'lumki, dostonlar o'zbek folklorining keng tarqalgan yirik janrlaridan biridir. Uning yaratilishi xalqimizning ma'naviy-maishiy qiyofasi, siyosiy qarashlari, axloqiy estetik tarbiya, adolat va haqqoniyat, ozodlik va tenglik, qahramonlik va vatanparvarlik haqidagi ideallari bilan chambarchas bog'likdir. Asriy kurashlar va ideallar mavzusi g'oyaviy mazmunni, voqelikning mohiyatini belgilaydi. «Doston» so'zi qissa, hikoya, sarguzasht, ta'rif va maqtov ma'nolarida ishlatiladi. Adabiy atama sifatida u, xalq og'zaki ijodida yirik hajmli epik asardir. Dostonlarda o'tmishimizdagi kishilar, joy nomlari, tog', suv havzalari nomlari, urug' nomlari qayd etilgan bo'ladi. Xususan, “Alpomish” dostonini o'qir ekanmiz, tariximiz ko'z oldimizda gavdalanadi. Tarixda o'zbek urug'lari, ular yashagan hududlar, tog'lar, ko'llar nomlarini uchratamiz.

“Alpomish” dostonidagi atoqli otlarni ma'nosiga ko'ra ikki xil nomlarni uchratish mumkin:

1. Ma'nosi aniq sezilib turuvchi nomlar. Bunda atoqli otlarning ma'nosi aniq sezilib turadi. Masalan: Burungi o'tgan zamonda, o'n olti urug' Qo'ng'iro't elida Dobonbiy degan o'tdi. Dobonbiydan Alpinbiy degan o'g'il farzand paydo bo'ldi. Alpinbiydan tag'i ikki o'g'il paydo bo'ldi: kattakonining otini

Boybo'ri qo'ydi, kichkinasining otini Boysari qo'ydi. Boybo'ri bilan Boysari — ikkovi katta bo'ldi. Boysari boy edi, Boybo'ri esa shoy edi, bul ikkovi ham farzandsiz bo'ldi.

2. Ma'nosi hozirda qorong'ilashgan ismlar. Atoqli otlarning ma'nosi hozirgi kunga kelib bir oz xiralashgan, ma'no anglashilishi qiyin bo'ladi. Masalan: Qalmoqshohning Tovka degan qizi bor edi. Alpomish aytdi: — o'g'rining piri hazrati Joltong deguchi edi, hazrati Joltonga sirina qolgin .

Xalq dostonlaridan yana biri "Ravshan" dostonini kuzatar ekanmiz atoqli otlarni ko'plab ma'no turlarini uchratishimiz mumkin: "Burungi o'tgan zamonda, el-yurti omonda, o'zi qibla tomonda, Buxorodan (joy nomi) tubanda, Taka Yovmit(joy nomi) deganda, Yovmit(joy nomi) elida, Chambilning(joy nomi) belida Go'ro'glibek(shaxs nomi) davrini surib o'tdi, dushmanning dodini berib o'tdi. qirq yigitni yig'ib; dovulni tuyib, oltin piyolaga maylar quyib, araqga bolni qotib, bolga araqni qotib, qirq yigitni yig'dirib, silovsin to'n kiydirib, kuniga kechkisin sergo'sht qilib, sermoyli palovga to'ydirib, semiz qo'ydan so'ydirib, ko'pkarisin cho'ptirib, olomonga ola sarpo yoptirib, el-xalqning ko'nglin toptirib, Yunus(shaxs nomi) bilan Misqol parini(shaxs nomi) Kohi Qofdan(joy nomi), Iram(joy nomi) bo'gidan keltirib, pari bilan o'ynab-kulib, davrini surib, umr o'tkarar edi. Go'ro'g'libekka(shaxs nomi) xudo farzand bermadi, oti ochmadi. Shunda Go'ro'glibek: «Asli taqdir-qismatda bizga farzanddan taqsim bo'lgan yurt ekan» deb taqdirga tan berib, Xasanxonni(shaxs nomi) Vayangandan(joy nomi), Avazxonni(shaxs nomi) Xunxordan(joy nomi) olib kelib ikkovini ulim deb, iskasam gulim debu jonu dilim deb, tobutimning chegasi, el-yurtimning egasi, olsam merosxorim deb, ikkovi bilan ko'nglini xush qilib, shularga bino qo'yib, «bolam-bo'tam» deb parvarish qilar edi."

Xulosa qilib aytganda, o'zbek xalq dostonlarida atoqli otlarning leksik guruhlarini va grammatik guruhlarini tahlil qilarkanmiz bu soha ancha qiziqarli shu bilan birga o'z mutaxassisidan yuksak mahorat va bilim ko'nikma o'z navbatida anchagina izlanish mehnat talab qiladi.

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PhD

XITOIY TOPISHMOQLARINING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI

Har qanday topishmoq jumboqqa to'la, uni yechishga intilgan shaxs yanada mukamallashadi.

J.R.Faulz

Annotatsiya: Maqolada xitoy topishmoqlarining shakllanishi va rivojlanish bosqichlari haqida fikr yuritiladi. Topishmoqlarning semantic-funksional tuzilishi va struktur tuzilishi o'rganib chiqiladi.

Topishmoq ilm-fanni o'rganish bilan bir qatorda, o'zining chuqur ma'noga ega teoriyasi va murakkab asosiga ega.

Kalit so'zlari: topishmoqlar, yozilish qonunlarini, Xitoy xalqi madaniyati

Topishmoqlar teoriyasining ildizi uning amalda qo'llanilishiga bog'liq. Xitoyda topishmoqlarning kelib chiqishi juda uzoq davrni o'z ichiga oladi, taxminan 3500 mingdan ortiq yillik tarixga ega.

Har bir sohada va ilm-fanni o'rganishda aniq qolipga solingan o'rganish obyekti mavjud, asosan maxsus o'rganiladigan ilm-fan sohasiga nazar tashlaydigan bo'lsak, Mao Tze Dun “矛盾论” “Qarama-qarshiliklar” asarida yozishicha: “Ilm-fanni o'rganishdagi farq, ilm-fanda turli xil yutuqlar bo'lganidek, unda kamchiliklar ham mavjud bo'ladi”¹, deb ta'kidlab o'tgan. Shuningdek, “Agar siz bilmaydigan qarama-qarshiliklar uchrasa, biror-bir predmetning harakatidan yoki ko'rinishidan uning qanday predmet ekanligini aniqlab olishingiz mumkin” deb yozilgan. Topishmoqlar insonlarning jamiyat hayotidagi, madaniyatidagi oldingi davrlardan qolgan boylik hisoblanadi, topishmoqlar madaniyatdagi boshqa xalq og'zaki ijodi na'munalaridan farq qiladi. Topishmoqlarning aytilishi va yozilishi maxsus qolipga solingan bo'ladi, topishmoqlarni yozishda uning yozilish tartibiga e'tibor berilishi lozim. Qonun-qoidasi esa aniq va ravshan yaratilishi kerak. Agar kelajakda topishmoqlarni yozishni bir ilm turiga kiritsak, unda maxsus o'rganishni tahlil qilishimiz kerak, uning asosiy negizini aniqlab odatdagi

yozilish qonunlarini aniqlab, topishmoqlar yozilishini kelajakda rivojlantirish lozim.

1 柳忠良“中华灯谜学”。北京：学苑出版社。2014年

Topishmoqlar Xitoy xalqining ko'p uchraydigan adabiyotning bir mashhur turi bo'lib, topishmoqlarni o'zining mustaqil tuzilishiga va ma'noviy yorqinligiga ega san'atning bir turi deyish ham mumkin. Topishmoqlar Xitoy xalqi madaniyatining yorqin ma'noga va tuzilishiga ega bo'lgan san'ati hisoblanadi. Bunday teoriyani o'qib foydalanganda, topishmoqlarning teoriyasida asarning rivojlanishiga katta e'tibor beriladi. Ularning rivojlanishi maxsus ma'noga egaligi bilan ifodalanadi.

谜学的研究氛围

Topishmoqlarni o'rganish uslubi: Topishmoqlarni o'rganish ham o'ziga xos ilm-fanning bir turidir, ular chuqur amalda qo'llaniladigan asosga egaligini bildiradi. Topishmoqlar teoriyasining kelib chiqishi uning amalda qo'llanilishiga bog'liq. Xitoy topishmoqlari Sun va Min sulolalari davrida rivojlandi, ularning soni ortib bordi. Bu bir necha yuz yillar ichida topishmoqlarni o'rganish teoriyasini ikki davrga bo'linishiga sabab bo'ldi:

清末民国，谜理论萌芽时期

Xulosa qilib shuni aytadigan bo'lsak, Xitoyda topishmoqlar tuzib, ularni o'rganish san'ati qadimiy davrlardan taraqqiy eta boshlagan. O'sha davrlardan oq topishmoq ilmiga bo'lgan qiziqish yuqori bo'lgan. Buni yozilgan asarlar va ularni tahlili jarayonida ham kuzatishimiz mumkin. Topishmoqlar ustida ishlash hozirgi kunda ham davom etmoqda va tilshunoslik sohasiga o'zining izchil hissasini qo'shmoqda deb aytishimiz mumkin.

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ИСТИҚБОЛЛИ “ИШОН” СЕЛЕКЦИЯ НАВИ ТОЛАСИДАН ОЛИНГАН ИПЛАРНИНГ ПИШИҚЛИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИ

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Тошкент тўқимачилик ва енгил саноат институти

Maqolada istiqbolli “Ishonch” selektsiya navi tolasining HVI tizimida aniqlangan sifat ko'rsatkichlari asosida ipning pishiqlik ko'rsatkichlarini hisoblash natijalari keltirilgan

В статье представлены результаты расчета прочности пряжи на основе показателей качества, определяемых по системе HVI волокна перспективного селекционного сорта «Ишонч».

The article presents the results of calculating the strength of the yarn based on quality indicators determined by the HVI system of the fiber of the promising breeding variety "Ishonch".

Пахта ва бошқа турдаги экинларни етиштиришда тез-тез ва узоқ давом этадиган қурғоқчилик туфайли, ундан ташқари кучли шамоллар, юқори ҳарорат ва ҳавонинг нисбий намлигининг пасайиши ҳосилдорликка салбий таъсир қилмоқда. Шунинг учун сув танқислигининг ҳосилга салбий таъсирини камайтириш усулларида бири бундай шароитда юқори сифатли толани сақлаб қолиш, пахта навларининг юқори ҳосилдорлиги ва экологик салбий омилларга чидамли қилиб яратиш ва ишлаб чиқаришга жорий этишдир [1,2].

Ўз ФАнинг Генетика ва экспериментал биология институти олимлари томонидан янги пахта селекция нав (“Зафар”, “Занги-Ота-2”, “Ишонч”)ларига патент олинган. “Зафар” нави эртапишар ва толасининг сифати юқорилиги билан, “Занги-Ота-2” нави тола чиқиши ва турли шароитларга чидамлилиги билан, “Ишонч” нави эса эртапишар, ҳосилдорлиги юқори, сувсизликка ва шўрланган ер шароитларига чидамлилиги билан ажралиб туриши таъкидланган [3].

Сувсизликка ва шўрланган шароитларга чидамли бўлган пахта толаси физик-механик кўрсаткичларини ўрганиш ва тўқимачилик саноатида самарали фойдаланиб, сифатли маҳсулотлар ишлаб чиқариш мақсадга мувофиқдир.

Илмий тадқиқот ишлари янги Ишонч селекция нави ва таққослаш учун назорат нави Бухоро 102 пахта толасида намуналар танлаб олинди. Синов ишлари “Пахтасаноат илмий маркази” АЖ синов

лабораториясида HVI 1000 тизимида олиб борилди. Тадқиқот натижалари 1-жадвалда келтирилди.

Ўтказилган синов натижалари таҳлилидан кўриниб турибдики, Ишонч селекция нави Бухоро 102 навига нисбатан микронейр 2,3%га, солиштирма узилиш кучи 4,3%га, юқори ўртача узунлик 2,6%га, сарғишлик даражаси бўйича 11,1%га камлиги ва ифлос аралашмалар миқдори 27,6%га, калта толалар индекси 23,9%га юқорилиги аниқланди.

1-жадвал

Сувсизликка чидамли селекция нави пахта толаси сифат кўрсаткичлари таҳлили

Селекция тури	Микронейр	Солиштирма узилиш кучи, %	Юқори ўртача узунлик, мм	Калта толалар индекси	Ифлос аралашмалар миқдори, %	Сарғишлик даражаси	Сувсизликка чидамлилик, %
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
О'zDst 604:2016 талаблари: 5 тип I нав учун	3,5-4,9	23,0-27,8	1,1-27,9-33,02	-	-	55-85	3,5-18,5
Бухоро 102	4,49	3,2,40	28,18(1,1)	9,51	22,33	79,48	7,85
Ишонч	4,6	3,1,05	27,44(1,08)	7,67	17,50	80,36	8,84
Фарқи, %	2,3	4,3	2,6	2,3,9	27,6	1,09	11,1

Демак, Ишонч пахта селекция нави O'zDst 604:2016 талабларига кўра

5 тип I навга мос келди ва бу толадан сифатли ип йигириш мумкин [4].

Йигирилган ип сифатини ва уни ишлаб чиқариш технологик жараёнларини башорат қилишда CSP ва Rkm кўрсаткичлари ипнинг турига боғлиқ ҳолда SITRA ташкилоти ишлаб чиқарган ва тавсия қилган формулалардан фойдаланиб ҳисобланади.

Ип пишиқлигини башорат қилишда узунлиги R_{km} кўрсаткичидан фойдаланилади. Ушбу кўрсаткич ҳалқаро USTER стандартларига киритилган. Ушбу кўрсаткич ипнинг километрдаги узунлиги бўлиб ўз оғирлиги таъсирида узунлигини англайди. Ушбу катталик узиш кучи кўрсаткичига тенг бўлиб гр/текс да ифодаланади [5].

Толанинг чизиқий зичлиги $T_T = M / 24,4$, 50% қоплама узунлик $L_{50} \{ \ell_{um} = 34 / 35 = 29,37 \}$, инглиз номери $N_e(C) = 318$. HVI тизимида кўрсаткичлардан толанинг ўртача узунлиги маълум бўлса CSP қуйидаги формула ўрдамида топилади:

$CSP = [280 \cdot \sqrt{FQI} + 700 - 13 \cdot C]$ карда ипи учун, (1) бу ерда, $FQI = L \cdot S \cdot m / f$ тола сифатининг индекси.

L – 50% ли қоплама узунлиги, мм; m -пишиб етилганлик коэффициенти, %; S -толанинг нисбий мустаҳкамлиги, сN/текс; f -микронейр қиймати; C -ипнинг инглизча номери.

HVI тизими синов натижаларидан фойдаланиб Rkm пишиқлиги қуйидагича аниқланади:

$$Rkm = 1,1 \left(\sqrt{FQI} \right) + 4,0 - \frac{13N_e}{150}, \quad [сН/текс] \quad (2)$$

$$FQI = \frac{L_{ar} \cdot R_{ar}}{M_{ar}}$$

бу ерда: L_{ar} , R_{ar} , M_{ar} - HVI тизимида аниқланган аралашма толаларининг кўрсаткичлари.

Тадқиқот қилинаётган пахта нави сифат кўрсаткичлари асосида юқорида келтирилган эмперик формулалар ўрдамида ипнинг пишиқлик кўрсаткичлари ҳисобланди (2-жадвал).

2-жадвал

Ипнинг пишиқлик кўрсаткичлари

.р	Вариант лар	Тол а узунлиги	То ла м икро- нейри	Ип нинг чизиқий зичлиги	Пишиқлик кўрсаткичлари		
					R{C } сN/текс	С SP	Rk m сN/ текс
	Бухоро 102	1,1	4,4 9	20	12, 8	2 623	17, 6
	Ишонч	1,08	4,6	20	12, 6	2 831	16, 26

Тадқиқот қилинаётган пахта навларисифат кўрсаткичлари асосида юқорида келтирилган эмперик формулалар ёрдамида ипнинг пишиқлик кўрсаткичлари ҳисобланди. 4-жадвалдан синалаётган толалар сифат кўрсаткичлари бўйича ип пишиқлик кўрсаткичлари Бухоро 102 навида юқори, лекин Ишонч нави USTER стандартларига мос келади.

Демак, эртапишар, ҳосилдорлиги юқори, сувсизликка ва шўрланган ер шароитларига чидамлили бўлган Ишонч нави пахта толасидан тўқимачилик саноатида самара фойдаланиш мумкин.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар рўйхати

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Abdulla Avloniyning ko`p qirrali faoliyatida yoshlarga ta'lim-tarbiya berish masalasidagi fikrlari

Aliqulova Layloxon Homid qizi.

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Annatsiya: Maqolamda millatimizning ilg`or kishilari qatori Avloniy Vatanning kelajagi yoshlar tarbiyasiga bog`liq ekanini, ularning ma'naviy barkamolligi yangi jamiyatning madaniy darajasini belgilashini chuqur anglagan.

Kalit sózlar: Ulug' zot, yaxshi xulq, tarbiyaning zamoni, badan tarbiya, fikr tarbiya, axloq tarbiya.

Abdulla Avloniy 1878-yilda Toshkent shahrida to'quvchi oilasida dunyoga keldi. Ijodkor o'zining ijtimoiy-siyosiy, ma'rifiy fikrlarini o'quvchi qalbiga joylashda nomlari yuqorida zikr etilgan milliy kuylar bilan bir qatorda «Na't», «Munojot» va «Hamd» kabi an'anaviy diniy qo'shiq janrlaridan ham foydalangan. Sharq xalqlari va xususan o'zbek, tojik va fors adabiyotida Ollah va uning so'nggi payg'ambarini sharaflovchi «Na't» va «Hamd» janrlari juda katta o'rin egallagan. Har bir yirik badiiy asarning boshida tangrini madh etuvchi parchalar (boblar) bo'lishi odat tusiga kirgan. «Na't» va «Hamd»lar aruz vaznida yoziladigan diniy musiqiy janrlar hisoblanadi. Bu asarlar qasida janriga hamohang bo'lib, to'ylarda va bazmlarda (konsertlarda) ijro etilgan. «Na't» va «Hamd»larning ohanglari bir tekisda ketib, qo'shiq va deklamatsiya o'rtasidagi usulda tanbur jo'rligida ijro etilgan. Asosiy urg'u so'zning mazmuniga qaratilgan bo'lib, tinglovchining his-tuyg'ulariga ta'sir qiladi. Avloniy bu holatni e'tiborga olgani uchun o'z she'riy to'plamlarida ulardan keng foydalangan. Shu sababli uning «Adabiyot yohud milliy she'rlar» to'plamining har bir ju'zi «Hamd» va «Na't»lar bilan boshlanadi. Avloniyning bir necha she'rlari «Na'ti Hazrati Rasuli Akram», «Hamd», «Na'ti sarvari olam», «Mustahzod» deb ataladi. Garchi bu she'rlar Ollah taolo va uning oxirgi paygambari Rasuli Akramga bag'ishlangan ta'rif, madhiya va iltijodan iborat bo'lsada, ammo shoir ularga zamonasiga oid ijtimoiy vazifalarni ham yuklaydi. Shu sababli ijroda xorni ham nazarda tutadi. Ma'lumki o'sha davrda ko'pgina yangi usuldagi maktablarda, o'quv kurslarida, musiqa darslari o'qitilgan va teatr badiiy havaskorligi rivojlantirilgan. Bunday muassasalarda Tavallo, Hoji Mu'in va Avloniyning axloq va odob, Vatanga muhabbat haqidagi she'rlari deklamatsiya qilingan hamda ashula sifatida aytilgan. «Sadoi Turkiston» gazetasining 1914 yil 20 iyun sonida bosilgan «Andijonda musulmoncha teatr» maqolasi

fikrimizni tasdiqlaydi. Maqolada jumladan shunday deyiladi: «Teatrdan so`ng erli musiqa bilan hamma o`ynovchilar sahnada hur ila Abdulla Avloniyning «O`qisin yoshlarimiz» asarini o`qib, xalqning olqishi va ofarinlariga musahhar bo`ldilar». Shunga o`xshash xabarlarini 1914-1916 yillardagi Toshkent va Farg`ona matbuotida juda ko`p uchratish mumkin. Umuman yangi mazmundagi she'riy asarlarni ma'lum kuylarga solib ijro etish o`sha davr madaniy hayotida keng miqyosda avj olgani kuzatiladi. Jadidchilik g`oyalari bilan sug`orilgan, yangi mazmundagi, ma'rifat, axloq, odob, millatparvarlikka chorlovchi mavzular xalq orasida ommalashgan bo`lib, asosan xalq qo`shiq va laparlari, maqom yo`lidagi uforlar, turkcha marshlar, tatarcha kuylar jo`rligida ijro etilishi odat tusiga kirgan. Tariximizning fojeali hodisalaridan biri 1916 yilning yozidarus podshosining Sibirga mardikorlikka olish haqidagi farmonining chiqishi bo`lgan. Ma'lumki bu tadbir o`lkamizning barcha hududlarida xalqning g`azabini, noroziligini qo`zg`ab, qo`zg`olonlarga olib keldi. Xalq orasida sodda va ommabop kuylarga solinib mardikorlikka, oq podshoga qarshi qaratilgan qo`shiqalar keng tarqalib ketdi. Jadid ziyolilari mustamlakachilar uyushtirgan beayov qirg`inlarni katta norozilik bilan qarshi oldilar. A.Avloniy ham «Mardikorlar ashuvlasi» turkumini yaratib, mardikorlik poeziyasiga o`z hissasini qo`shdi. To`plamga «Bir mardikorning otasi o`g`liga aytgan so`zlari», «Onasining o`g`liga aytgan so`zlari», «O`g`lining onasiga aytgan so`zlari», «Xotuniga aytgan so`zi» kabi ta'sirli, dardga to`la she'rlari kiritilgan bo`lib, ular ohangdor va ashulabop qilib yozilgan. Muallifning o`zi uni «Bir necha yangi kuylarga solinub yozilmish «Adabiyot» majmuasining 6-juz'i» deb atasada, ammo qaysi yangi kuylar haqida ran borayotganligi haqida xech narsa demaydi. Kitob so`zboshisida undagi she'rlarning 1916 yilgi mardikorlik voqeasi munosabati bilan ezilganligi va «Turon» to`dasi tomonidan aytilganligi ma'lum qilingan, xolos Yangi nashrda esa: «Birinchi to`da mardikorlarni jo`natmoq uchun chiqishda yasalgan namoyishda Toshkentdagi teatrdan maxsus «Turon» to`dasi tarafidan turli latif kuylarda o`qulgan edi. Ko`b kishilar iltimos qiluvchi sababli ja'm qililib, nashr qilindi. Va boshqa bir necha shoirlarning yozgan she'rlari o`zlarining ruxsatlari ila ushbu adabiyotga ilova qilindi» deyilgan. Demak, Abdulla Avloniy «Turon» truppassi tashkil topganidan boshlab, unga atab, ma'lum kuylarga moslab ko`pgina she'rlarni yozgan. Ashulalarning hammasiga Avloniyning o`zi kuylar tanlagan. Bu she'rlar o`sha kezlarda xalq orasida yoyilgan «Poezdingni jildirgan», «Nikolay qon jallob», «Mardikorlar voqeasi» kabi xalq qo`shiqalari yo`lida aytilgan bo`lishi mumkin.

Abdulla Avloniy «Adabiyot yohud milliy she'rlar», «Mardikorlar ashuvlasi» to`plamlarida o`zbek she'riyatining an'anaviy janrlarini mazmunan

va shaklan boyitdi. Ularga yangi ma'no va aniqrog'i minbar ohanglarini olib kirdi. Bu she'rlar o'zining ochiq ma'nosi, yorqinligi, oddiyligi, ta'sirchanligi, musiqaviyligi bilan ajralib turadi. 1914 yilda yozilgan «Millatga xitob» she'ri "Sharqiy kuylardan «So'yla bir ko'rki arab» kuyiga solinub yozildi" deb izohlangan. Sharqiy kuylar deb Avloniy vaqtida xalqimiz orasida ommabop bo'lgan turkcha marshlar nazarda tutilgan.

Avloniy 1917 yil fevral inqilobini Turkiston xalqlari uchun erk va ozodlik olib keladi, degan orzular bilan kutib oldi va ko'p marshlar («sharqiyalar») yozdi. Ammo u ko'pchilik ziyolilar qatori xalqining, Vatanning «porloq kelajagiga» ishonchini juda tez yo'qotadi va «hurriyat nomin eshitdim, lek adolat ko'rmadim» deb iztirob chekadi.

Qilur bizlardan, ey ahli Vatan, faryod Turkiston,
Hamma obod bo'ldi, bo'lmadi obod Turkiston.

O'z manfaatlarini ko'zlamasdan vatanini dunyoning eng taraqqiy etgan davlatlar qatorida ko'rish orzusi bilan yashagan shoir madaniyat va san'at orqali har bir odamning yuragiga yo'l topa olish zarurligini tushungan va targ'ib etgan. Avloniy «Madaniyat to'lqinlari» maqolasida shunday yozadi: «Hozir yarim asrdurki madaniyat bizni orqamizdan quviyur. Biz qirdan-qirga qochurmiz, qarshimizda maishat mashaqqatlari chiqub hujum qilur, o'ngimizdan bilimsizlik va jaholat kelub jonlarimizni siqur, so'ngimizdan musriflik, faqirlik, bid'atlar chiqub yo'limizni to'sun». Bu holdan qutilish yo'lida «faqat birgina chorasi bordurki madaniyatni qabul qilmak va haqiqiy madaniyatga kirishmak lozim». Binobarin shoir ana shu madaniyatni barpo qilishda teatr va musiqaning o'zni va roli katta ekanini chuqur anglagan va uni xalq ongiga etkazishga intilgan. Uning san'at, xususan musiqa san'ati xaqidagi fikrlari, qarashlari ana shundan dalolatdir.

Avloniy badiiy-estetik qarashlarini, musiqaqa munosabatini bir maqola hajmida qamrab olish nihoyatda qiyin. Ammo ushbu muxtasar yondashuvning o'ziyoq adibning milliy ananaviy musiqa bilimdonlaridan hamda xazinabonlaridan biri bo'lgan deyishimizga to'liq asos beradi.

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**METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AND
THE ROLE OF INTEGRAL EDUCATION
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Abstract: Nowadays there is a growing necessity of highly qualified and flexible professionals. They have to possess a good knowledge of foreign languages to be able to communicate with colleagues from different countries. Thus, teachers of foreign language are in constant search for the most effective ways of training. In this paper, the authors analyze the process of teaching foreign (English) language to Bachelor students and identify the most effective ways of teaching communication in professional sphere. The study use a critical analysis of the literature on the problem, monitoring of the process of teaching foreign language, generalization of the authors' own experience of teaching. The authors define an important role of modern media in the foreign language teaching and develop a program of teaching the English language to Bachelor students using media educational environment.

Keywords: foreign language, Bachelor students, Bachelor's program, media educational environment, professional communication.

Every citizen of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan must be able to read the original literature in a foreign language, understand the text and use it in their profession. He should also be able to communicate freely in a foreign language with his interlocutor on a given topic. After all, learning foreign languages is a requirement of today's globalized era.

Due to independence, special attention is paid to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. Thousands of foreign language teachers have been trained, all conditions have been created for staff training in our country and abroad, multimedia textbooks in English, German and French, electronic resources for learning English have been prepared. The organization of language rooms is a clear proof of this. On the basis of improving the education of the younger generation in foreign languages and the training of specialists who are fluent in these languages a lot of work is being done.

Learning English is becoming a priority of the modern education system. Open cultural and social doors for those who speak this language are all open to economic doors, because the use of English creates more opportunities for reading and working. The latter is highly valued in the

context of the competitiveness of each country's labor market. At a time when the development of science is accelerating, interdisciplinary integration plays a crucial role in the establishment of continuing education. The term integration is derived from the Latin word *integrate*, meaning to join, to unite. Data integration involves combining and presenting materials available from different sources for a specific purpose.

Integration, on the other hand, is based on interdisciplinary communication, that is, on the knowledge gained in general in the sciences, academic disciplines, their sections and topics. means opening. That integrated learning has its place in English language teaching we can observe. The teacher's child thinking and different areas its role in arousing interest also justifies itself in this approach.

From this interdisciplinary communication will also increase significantly. In various parts of the education system, pre-school children, primary school students (ages 7-11) and high school students are learning a foreign language. An integrated approach can be used in primary education along with game technology. For high school students, thinking is also a factor in broadening their horizons.

Management of computer networks such as the Internet is necessary in various production and leisure systems. Thus, there is a need to introduce these technologies into pedagogical practice as part of a new teaching strategy. Thus, the use of technology in the language teaching process leads to greater efficiency.

In order to integrate the solution of a problem based on interdisciplinary communication, the teacher must first clearly define the goal, review the material to be studied, select appropriate methods for its effective mastering, determine the form and organization of the lesson process and it is required to predetermine the results to be obtained.

What is the most important thing in improving your students ability of learning a foreign language? Through out the findings which I have found during the researches on teaching English crucial was that for many students isn't only new world, new way of life, new people and of course new opportunities but also the tool changing them mentally and psychologically. So, how to involve your students in English learning atmosphere requires you much effort. Immersing your students in the target language helps them use it more independently and this can lead to increase confidence and better vocabulary. Students enjoy listening to ' real people ' speaking the target language, so get our colleagues involved.

Firstly, you can start with encouraging students and staff to use the language. Even if they make mistakes, and emphasize that communication is the key. You could invite a fluent speaker into the classroom, perhaps a friend or a colleague from another school, as a guest. Anything show the target language being used in practical situations will emphasize the value of the language as a communicative tool. If we take into consideration grammar, grammar translation method lately has been considered as an old method of teaching and it has also advantages. Grammar is the foundation for building language skills. Learning grammar enables students to speak and write more accurately, confidently and fluently. I have found that asking students to explain grammar rules to each other and to the rest of the class gives them more confidence. The more you learn, use and practice the language , the more accurate and fluent you become. Repetition and practice are essential to many skills , and this is especially true when learning a language. I want to indicate that one of the best ways to learn English is reading. Reading is a learned skill, but good reading relies on more than how we were taught to read. Reading improves writing, writing improves reading. Also, by reading you revise widen what you know and learn what you weren't aware of before.

All things considered, the more you learn and teach , use and practice the language , the more accurate and fluent your students become. Repetition and practice are essential to many skills, and this is especially true when learning a language.

Given the goals and objectives of teaching English in higher education, they can be divided into 2 groups:

1. Foreign language - universities, institutes, faculties that train specialists in English.
2. Foreign language - non-philological education that does not train a specialist in English institutions.

The goals of teaching English in these 2 groups are different, and in the first group of higher education institutions, English is taught in depth, both theoretically and practically, due to the training of English language specialists. In the second group, non-philological educational institutions, there is a complex goal in English. The goal is for the student to receive a general education in English and to teach him / her to use English in his / her future work in his / her specialty. Partial communication in the profession involves learning to read and translate texts by learning words related to their specialty.

Teaching foreign languages in higher education institutions includes 1) practical or communicative, 2) general education, 3) education, 4) the use of acquired skills and abilities for other purposes, development goals. General educational, pedagogical and developmental goals occur in the realization of the communicative goal. Let's take a closer look at these 4 goals:

1. Communicative (practical) goal: Through this goal, students develop skills in English language materials. Students lexical, grammatical pronunciation should be able to apply the materials independently in speech. English speaking, reading, writing skills are developed.

2. General educational purpose: Through this purpose to further develop students' thinking, to receive and impart information in English, to gain a deeper understanding of English, new knowledge of English and the history and literature of the people of the country where the language is studied and broadening students 'worldviews through the acquisition of insights and information about their culture. Students 'understanding, growth of thinking, broadening of their worldview will be at the expense of a foreign language or in English.

3. Educational goal: This goal is to provide international, moral and aesthetic education in a foreign language English class, as well as to cultivate an attitude to work.

4. Developmental goal: This goal defines the guidelines for learning, teaching students to know the student personally. It develops language analysis, generalization, independent reasoning, listening, speech, and movement skills. It teaches to imagine, to create a speech situation, to have a logical connection in speech, to be able to think independently, to understand the meaning of words, to work independently with a dictionary, manuals, and to take optional classes, develops independent preparation for extracurricular activities, their conduct. The four goals above are always complementary, in touch with each other. These four goals should be achieved through English language materials, speech activities, taught and repeated in each lesson.

Upon graduation, students are required to be able to accept, comprehend, and articulate an English opinion orally and in writing.

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